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**USING LOGICAL DATA WAREHOUSE IN THE PROCESS OF BIG DATA
INTEGRATION AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN ORGANISATIONAL SECTOR
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BY

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**THIS THESIS IS SUBMITTED TO THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND
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DECLARATION

I, Chisom Ernesther Offia , do hereby declare that, with the exception of my reference to other people’s work which have been duly acknowledged, the work contained in this thesis, “ Using Logical Data Warehouse In The Process Of Big Data Integration And Big Data Analytics In Organisational Sector” is the result of my research carried out under the supervision of the School Of Computing, Engineering And Physical Sciences, The University Of The West Of Scotland, Paisley, Scotland, from October 2017

to October 2021. I further declare that this thesis work, either in whole or in part, has not been presented for another degree in this University or elsewhere.

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ABSTRACT

This thesis first reviews different aspects of big data management, including data integration and traditional data warehouse, and their associated challenges. In many enterprises today, strategic information plays an increasingly important role in helping decision makers reach or justify decisions about their business. An effective decision-making process benefits from data that is frequently extracted from several heterogeneous data sources. Big data development affects enterprises across various sectors [81]. The data extracted are from various databases which are from different organisation systems and this has resulted in organisation managers dealing with issues of integrating several databases from independent data sources with different semantic or no canonical concept description. The increase of data volume, high speed of data generation and the increasing growth of different data from heterogeneous sources have led to data warehouse implementations that are relatively unresponsive to real-time changes in the business environment. Data warehouses are most valuable assets for enterprises which deal with a lot of business information. Given the volume of data dealt with, consuming too many resources can be expensive to acquire and maintain. Data warehouses mainly store historical and current business data for decision making. Data integration in today's world is more than just integration, the need for data integration is now to offer reusable data integration solutions and a complete innovative portfolio of data capabilities in a fast-moving ecosystem [83]. Problems included in big data integration are the increased duplications of data especially unwanted or unused data and has resulted in data redundancy, problem like data accessibility to regulatory bodies or agencies for finding out trends or statistics of a particular challenge faced in a city to carry out proper decision making, cost of data transformation and movement from heterogeneous sources into a central database, especially in the big data environment.

This research addresses the problem of conflicting data formats. This thesis employed the use of questionnaire (interview questions) which were sent out to different public organisations. Responses from staff of several public organisations were used to compare and formulate different scenarios and construct suitable case study. The use of the questionnaire gave the researcher the ability to see and identify the common challenges in their various organisations, compared their challenges with their current data integration management tools, studied each of their business requirements and drew conclusions as to whether Data Virtualisation will be the best solution to their business requirements. At the end of the qualitative approach and literature review, the research was able to portray that ETL techniques is widely used, and there is little or no knowledge about Logical data warehouse as an alternative approach to an organisation. The research was also able to elaborate the difference between the traditional data warehouse and logical data warehouse using the demonstration of prototype, showing the advantages of data virtualization over ETL techniques. The prototype also reveals the importance of SLAs construction and SLAs' requirement involved in the achievement of the framework. This research also finds out that Service Level Agreement (SLA) can be a solution to some of the v's of big data challenge which are the volume and variety and realised that there may be cost in maintaining SLAs between two parties.

Keywords: Big Data; Traditional Data warehouse; Logical Data warehouse; Benefits and Challenge

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND STUDY

The era of *big data* is broadly one in which information is available from a “cyber universe” comprising billions of digital sources, whose data is generated by people and machines in structured and unstructured forms [1]. This big data era has now resulted in datafication meaning the digitization and analytics of big data [2]. Big data as defined by [3] is the integration of several disciplinary technologies which facilitate customers by gathering a wide range of services in one application. The phrase Big Data applies where the volume, velocity and variety of data exceeds a firm’s storage or the capability to compute correctly and to facilitate timely decision making [4]. Big Data Integration therefore needs to address the additional problems of volume, velocity, variety, and veracity.

The world is currently facing an expansion in the size and variety of digital data which are generated by both human (user) and machine (system). The growth in communication from data sources in the “Internet of Things” has had a great impact on how big data has developed. Examples of digital data *varieties* are big data in the health sector where data is retrieved from different sources like Electronic records (ER), patient DB, clinical trials, medical measurement, and imaging [5]. Big data is also characterized by *velocity*, the speed rate at which newly collected data is added, the frequency with which the content of data sources changes with time, and the rapid growth in the number of data sources. It is observed that data sources are generally heterogeneous in their format, exhibiting large *variety* even for similar entities. Data sources are of different quality and differ in the coverage, accuracy, and timeliness of the data they provide [6].

The purpose of *data integration* is to combine data from different sources or departments with big data to provide a unified access to decision makers and facilitate the use of the resulting information across the different parts of an organization. The idea of *Big Data Integration* is the combination traditional data integration applied to big data and this makes traditional data integration different from big data integration. This means that the big data challenges now need to be considered when integrating data.

Data warehousing involves data integration, and generally creating a new combined data set containing data gathered from many sources using the Extract, Transform, Load approach (ETL). According to [1] they agree that ETL technology tends to be the best approach used by many organizations in managing and sustaining the transportation of data. These researchers [4] report that most firms spend more time on data manipulation and most often data that are stored are not being used and some data that the organization has, or retrieves is not utilized properly. According to these researchers, such factors lead to unnecessary costs and limited usability of the extracted. Another challenge of data integration is structural integration. This is related to the heterogeneity of a data model which is often related to legacy systems, and this is where a new data model is created to combine the different data model is implied by heterogeneous sources or legacy systems. Often, legacy systems contain out-of-date data and cannot accept new requirements and technologies because they are no longer managed by staff who understand them [7].

1.2 SCOPE OF THE RESEARCH

This research focuses on the integration of data from different organisations or departments into one virtual database using *logical data warehousing* technology including view-mediated

data integration. Applying *data virtualisation*, data analytics can be carried out in real-time, by transferring from data sources and manipulating only the summary data immediately required.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the problems associated when tools such as ETL precede big data analytics?
2. How will logical data warehouse be a solution to the V's (Volume, Velocity, Variety, of Big Data)?
3. How should the problem of conflicting data formats and semantics (units, categories) be addressed?

1.4 AIM/ OBJECTIVE

The Aim of this Research is to

- Discuss data integration strategies that enhance data validity and reduce complexity in the process of data integration (Big data Variety challenge) and reduce data redundancy (Big data Volume challenge).
- Consider how a centralised virtual database could be used in an organisation such as smart city department,
- Consider the benefits of big live data integration (Logical data integration) model for near real-time analytics (Big Data Velocity challenge).

The Objectives of this Research is to

- Develop the use of Service Level Agreements (SLA's) and its content to reduce data complexity and enhance data validity
- Use a Prototype implementation approach: a case study to show the process of data extraction and virtual data integration which can be adopted in an organisation sector
- Design an interview questionnaire to acquire any challenges and perhaps any new challenge with their current tools and Design both a data virtualisation model and traditional data warehouse model to perform comparison

1.5 RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS

Some of the challenges that were highlighted in this research was data complexity which is as a result of unprecedented large-scale samples which appears in diversified data types and patterns and are in various data quality. The high dimensionality of data combined with large sample size of data has created these problems such as heavy computational cost and complexity. This research has implemented the use of data virtualisation which reduces complexity by tackling data volume in a way of promoting data from various sources should be kept in their various sources. This was achieved by designing a prototype using C# programming language and Microsoft SQL language to describe how the research framework works. Also, the new approach demonstrated the use of SLA which agrees the data format and data type that each data contributor will design their database to be in. This method also reduced data complexity as well. The research also applied the qualitative approach by sending out interview questionnaire including telephone interviews to recognise the common tools that are adopted by most organisations and to acquire different challenges faced when using their current analytical tools. The research also did comparison on both the traditional data

warehouse prototype and the framework's approach prototype to illustrate the cost involve in both and draw conclusion.

1.6 STRUCTURE OF THE DISSERTATION

Following this introductory chapter, the other chapters are as follows; Chapter 2 describes the general models that govern most of the proposed framework from the literature of big data management, data warehouse, background of data integration and its architecture. This final stage of this chapter is the literature review on the challenges surrounding the process of data integration with the focus on highlighting the gaps identified.

Chapter 3 explains the overview of the proposed model of Big Data Integration; explains the one of the previous works (RESTView and RESTif) what it entails and the process that will be involved, also highlighted the framework in achieving the proposed model of data integration.

Chapter 4 contains the methods of achieving this research. These methods include the Qualitative approach and the Prototype Implementation approach. The Qualitative approach outlines the use of interview questions to answer one of the research questions. The Prototype Implementation approach uses the DAMS business case study to demonstrate the effect of virtual data integration.

Chapter 5 outlines the research benefit and the limitations, conclusion of the study and its recommendations of future research directions.

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CHAPTER TWO: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents an overview of the studies into different research areas which are Big Data, Data Warehouse, Data integration and Logical Data Warehouse. It focuses on data integration as the main context and explores the data extraction process within the integration of data from heterogeneous sources. It also considers software to achieve virtual data integration or logical data warehouse in order to minimise data redundancy and promote easy accessibility to data sources in an efficient way. Therefore, this research will be able to provide breadth by combining different sectors and depth by targeting an implementation approach.

2.1.2 Research Terminologies Used

Big Data: Big data is defined by [158] using the 3Vs model (Volume, Velocity and Variety) as a generation of new techniques and architecture, designed to extract value from very high volume of data which appears in variety of forms in order to capture data in high velocity and analysis. Big data is also defined by [159] as the high volume, high velocity and high variety of information assets that need new techniques and architectures to enable enhanced decision making and analysis.

Data Integration: Data Integration is defined as the process of combining data from different sources or departments with big data to provide a unified access to decision makers and facilitate the use of the resulting information across the different parts of an organization [6].

Data warehouse: A data warehouse is a central repository or physical location where integrated information that originates from one or more sources are migrated into or stored. The data integrated from different sources can be structured data, semi-structured data and unstructured data [45]; [46].

Data Virtualisation: This is a new approach or technology that allows the placement of an additional layers to enable unified access to heterogeneous data from different organisations in real-time. Data virtualisation (DV) is closely related to virtual databases or mediators, provides data stakeholders a virtual data layer over data infrastructure of the organisation [160].

Service Level Agreement: A Service level agreement (SLA) is a contract that is between two or more parties that is agreed on a specific service provided. The agreement should specify accepted or unaccepted service levels that falls between the data provider and the data consumers [58]; [59].

2.2 BIG DATA

Big data is characterized by Six V's; Volume (which refers to the size of data which has expanded beyond terabytes), Velocity (which refers to the speed of product of data to meet different demands), Variety (which refers to data generated from diverse sources and these data are unstructured which make them difficult to categorize), Veracity (which highlights the significance of addressing data uncertainty and managing it), Value (which refers to the significant advantage that big data can offer to business) [98];[99]; [100]. Some authors in [100] added validity as the correctness or how valid the data is to the city.

2.2.1 Volume

This refers to the size of data which is generated every second [101]. The size is no longer reckoned in terabytes but petabyte. At this level, datasets become too large to manage, store and analyse using the traditional database technology because of its size. The reason for the large data size is because of the increasing number of people sharing, communicating and accessing data through different devices. Also, there are many sensors being connected as internet of things [102]. According to the research by [103], in four (4) billion number of people utilizing mobile phone have the percentage of 12 making use of smartphones whereby the percentage increases by twenty (20) each year. Another research [82] outlines that, thirty (30) million networked sensor nodes are currently in utilities, transportation, automotive, industrial, and retail sectors.

The challenge: The rapid increase in large-scale data has led to new challenges in data mining techniques, data management, data integration, data processing, and data retrieving. This now requires novel approaches to addressing the big data issues [82]. The data ubiquity, dynamic nature of different data generation resources and heterogeneity of data has created a challenging task in integrating, processing, and retrieving [113].

Hadoop is one framework created from MapReduce and Big-Table for the purpose of allowing parallel processing in groups of high latency and this system has tolerance requirements for any failure and load assessment [104].

2.2.2 Variety

Some of the data today are structured and unstructured. This means data variety is referred to as different type of data from different sources [105]. Examples are data sources from text messages and video [101]. In the past, structured data focused on data arrangements done easily by fitting it into rows, tables, or relational databases.

The challenges faced: In a variety of big data, enterprises face issues when analysing. Enterprises continue to automate further business processes, and this disrupts the design of data systems. Another challenge that, data appears in different forms and data quality and that alone shows the heterogeneity as a natural property of big data (For example: when data coming from different country like USA, UK, Nigeria, and there is a table for individual address from these sources, the Postcode known to UK is Zip code for another country and County known in UK is State in another country) and it is a big challenge to comprehend. Enterprise faces difficulty on how to sort these different data to be readable by end users without creating ambiguous results [106]. Since different data comes from different sources, many cases report both relevant information and some information that needs proper filtering. Therefore, a reliable system is needed to identify impactful information. The size of data does not consistently follow a specific template or format and these different forms led to poor data quality which requires a clear indication that diversity is a natural property of big data [82].

2.2.3 Velocity

This refers to how fast new structured data is generated and at what speed these data move around [105]; [106]; [101]. For example: in social media services, we observe how fast it is generated from different sources.

The challenges related to velocity include the requirement to manage the high influx rate of non-homogeneous data. Another example is Internet of Things (IoT) from smart city which is connected to Sensors and these sensors will be constantly channelling tiny bits of data at near

constant rate. And as the number of flow increases, so is the flow and speed of data. Data from mobile apps like google map for transportation generate floods of information that can be utilized through real-time data and the pattern and behaviour of data can be observed [82]. Cloud computing was designed with the promise to solve the data storage and its processing time challenges [104].

2.2.4 Veracity

This is the management of data uncertainty, if data is not accurate it will create errors in analysis and that will be a problem for the organization [107]. With the generation of data which constantly changes, the quality and accuracy of data are uncontrollable. Therefore, big data technology has made the quality and accuracy less controllable. Understanding data from different sources is more important when relating to veracity. IBM analysed the characteristics of data which denotes untrustworthiness inherited in many sources of both structured and unstructured data [82]. In decision making, veracity and the frequency of how data is generated (velocity) is a great challenge.

Nevertheless, it is important that data should be sampled for operational decision making and veracity should be considered by identifying the risk and complexity it poses when constructing an operational decision [108]. Example of this risk and complexity can be general lack of experience expert, toolsets, methods and best practices and the impact it might have is potential huge margin of error in budgeting for example budget during economic crises during this pandemic. Another example of risk posed is conflicting user requirements which can result in not meeting user requirements. Another risk posed is scalability issues due to huge amount of data and can lead to poor system performance.

2.2.5 Value

Research considers value as an essential feature within data when extracted from multiple sources to make meaningful data out of them. Also, value of information can be quantified by how often information is used in decision making. For example, weekly reports that are not read by management have little value: a good summary might be better if the issues summarised are still of prime concern. The Centre for Economics and Business Research (CEBR) in UK predicted that big data analysis will be beneficial to the retail, manufacturing, financial and public sectors [109]; [102]. Value depends on thorough analysis of accurate and valid data because the data increases rapidly. It is messy seeing that data constantly changes in different thousands of formats which are worthless without analysis [110]. To ensure good practice of data utilization, it is important to have efficient big data management tools in place. These management tools should be able to recognize different formats of data from different sources, structuralize the unstructured data into groups, manage, classify, and control them [100]; [111]; [112].

2.2.6 Valency

This refers to the interconnection of data, also used to understand online consumers' behaviour and it raises the challenge of data security concern and task complexity in the aspect of analysis. In big data, valency measures the ratio of the actual connected data sets compared to the possible number of connections that could happen within the process of collection [114]. Firms can collect a large amount of sensitive information which can be targeted by attackers [115].

2.2.7 Big Data Challenges

The big data challenges are related to difficulty in understanding the data, decision making issues, issues of privacy, ethical consideration related to mining and the implementation of new approach. The big data challenges are categorised into three groups which are: characteristics of the data; the process challenges of data and the data management challenges.

Big data researchers face challenges on how data can be stored, managed, extracted and analysed constantly [1]. Big data are characterised by high dimensionality and large sample size, which is the variety and the velocity of big data and these two raise some unique features of challenges surrounding big data management. The high dimensionality combined with large sample size of data creates problems such as heavy computational cost and complexity. Other issues related to heterogeneity, statistical bias and experimental variation is as a result of data aggregated from multiple sources [161]. Data complexity is as a result of unprecedented large-scale samples when dealing with computational problems and this is characterised by diversified types and patterns, and greatly varied data quality. It extremely becomes difficulty when using traditional data analysis and mining task to tackle data retrieval, topic recovery, semantic analysis, and sentiment analysis [162].

This researcher [162] explained that, new approaches for big data will need to provide a framework that will address computational complexity such as highly efficient computing paradigms, proving a method for processing and analysing big data and promoting value-driven applications in specified domains.

Another researcher [116] highlighted that big data do not only rely on archiving and conserving large quantity of data but accessing these data in an efficient way. The solution to this problem was the use of Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) which is stated that it is fault-tolerant because the loaded file is replicated three times [116]. The problem found with this HDFS model is that replication of data three times increases the demand for storage space.

This paper by [2] outlines challenges relating to the management of big data in government. These challenges are storage and computational complexity, ensuring transparency and lastly the formidable analysis of voluminous data. The researcher further explained that it is difficult for data analysis to be done properly since government data are stored in silos which are being managed by different departments.

Another challenge of big data in analytical aspect spotted by [102] is the access and sharing of information. They further explained the reason why the access to data and data sharing a challenge is because of security issues of the clients' data and one getting to know the operation of the company [102]. Data collected for analysis typically lacks basic structure and some values of the data are missing. This is as a result of data that is managed by people who do not understand the particular data, and this has also been a challenge [99]; [2]. Variety in big data has led to data inconsistency resulting to analytics sprawl and poor data quality [6]. The high velocity of data has generated challenges relating to speed handling the speed of new data or updated data that are constantly generated.

Cities face challenges when relating to big data and these challenges are in different forms; they are privacy and security, data quality, collection of data, data sharing, analysis of data from different sources, accessibility of data, management of data and many others.

TABLE 1. A brief listing of big data challenges and suggestions from researchers as solutions to big data problems [99]; [117]; [118]; [119].

TABLE 1. A brief listing of big data challenges and suggestions from researchers as solutions to big data problems

Big Data Attributes	Challenges related to	Suggested solutions
Volume	Data storage, Data scale, Data reduction	Data record, Sensors, Web Scraping, NoSQL, Apache Hadoop, Visualization, Spark, robust hardware, sharing data based on cloud
Variety	Data access,	Structure data and standardisation of units and categories
Velocity	Data collection,	Cloud using hybrid model, Sampling data.

Every department like e-government, city agencies have; their own data warehouse or silo of confidential information [100]. The collection of data, the processing stage, data transaction, data integration, transformation, data storage, data computation, and understanding data form the big data challenges with relation to analytics. In the aspect of organization, data acquisition is a challenging task which can lead to complexity, robustness, and security issues. The use of different technologies, devices and IoT, gave birth to the need of deep understanding of data. This prompted the need for data transformation. When these data are not in real-time, it produces incomplete data which in return compromises data accuracy. Therefore, data extracted from heterogenous sources of different physical devices need fast and real-time analysis [3].

Privacy and security of data is another challenge on its own in relation to big data. Sometimes there might be errors in the process and analysis of data which can lead to exposure of information about its users. That is the reason why individual access to data is impracticable. Suggestions have been made by some researchers [99] that encryption should be used to ensure safe transfer of data over the network. Databases may contain sensitive data which government uses, and this data demands high level of security policies and effective mechanism to protect it [100].

In reducing the challenges of access to data together with its security measures, policies are needed to ensure that all information is accessible fairly to consumers while validity and monitoring processes continue. Some people tend to make assumptions that access to data is a violation of person's privacy rights thereby creating high demand to clearly notify and protect privacy rights of citizens, organisations, and various departments of smart cities.

2.3 DATA INTEGRATION

Data integration started early in the 1980s for combining the different varieties of data sources often known as information silos [8]. The first method of data integration was carried out by the University of Minnesota in the year 1991 and was used for the Integrated Public Use Micro-Data Services (IPUMS). This applied traditional data warehouse technology and the ETL approach to integrate data into a unified schema [9].

In 2009, the approach of data integration changed to access and retrieval of data directly from a source database by applying Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) which relies on mapping. This mapping is done in two methods which are the GAV and LAV approach. The reason for the change of approach was as a result of changes to organization demands in accessing real-time data through a mediated means [10].

In 2010, some researchers sought to resolve semantic conflicts between heterogeneous sources, applying the use of ontologies which is represented as ontology-based data integration [10]. In 2011 data isolation was considered, resulting in the development of disparate data models. One method proposed by [11] to eliminate this issue was enhanced data modelling. This model was designed to reorganize the data model by augmentation and by structuring meta-data in a standard form of data entities.

Database integration can lead to a huge repository that provides user the opportunity to get desired information and requires detailed consideration of the heterogeneity and autonomy of data sources. [12]. The integration of data is as a result of query requests from data consumers and the information obtained after the queries are requested are consumed in two major forms. The first includes human readable forms such as charts, Microsoft Excel, parsable formats like JSON, XML CSV, and Microsoft Word documents [120]. The second form is the inbuilt system for the purpose of the consumers querying several disparate databases [13]; [14]; [15].

Figure 1 – Traditional data analytics which comprises of data acquisition, data integration, data warehousing, analytics, and presentations.

Data acquisition in figure 1 is the process of extracting information from the data source to and within the warehousing environment. Its actions are driven by the goals and aims of the data warehouse and therefore it is not an isolated activity. Data acquisition identifies the different

sets of data needed from the source, chooses the extraction approach, moves the specific data requested from the source, applies transformations, and then loads the data. Data acquisition uses the Extract Transform Load (ETL) tools [16]; [17].

In the process of traditional data warehouse architecture shown in figure1, data is extracted from the data sources, and extraction is done by retrieving all the required data directly from the source data.

The goal of Data integration as aims to overcome the information silo effect of the isolation of the data sources from each other, by direct copying of the data into a global database [8].

In figure 2 the different approaches of data integration are into different categories.

Data integration approaches

Figure 2: Categories of Integrated Approaches

The advancement of organizational needs in workflow includes data management, storage, maintenance, and data integration. Data integration is a complex issue for organizations in deploying big data architecture because of the heterogonous data formats they used [30]. Data integration usually focuses on the need of an organization, where the data is currently in silos in different departments of the organization. Data integration currently is often used by database vendors to combine data bases into one larger system, using Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) approach in creating the new combined data sets. ETL tool is one common form of data integration software used by many organizations. This is not always appropriate because of data protection issues and redundant data, and in any case, often results in data no longer being managed by people who understand it: the ETL process often loses important features of the data [18]; [7].

The goal of data integration is to provide unified access to data. For example using airport data source; if data resides in different databases and not integrated, customers will not be able to benefit from using a single mode of access to acquire diverse information related to the particular airport, but if data is integrated into single source like Air info, (where the information about the particular airport, airline, flight schedule, departure time, arrival time, run way used, airfare, and many more) it will be beneficial for a client to use one single mode

to view the required information. Such integration eliminates the need to query each data sources separately when extracting information [20] but these researchers [6] also elaborated that integrating multiple data sources into a single system can be difficult to achieve and that will require some amount of manual effort to understand the format of the data present in each source.

A mediator approach provides a global view that combines data by integrating different views of different databases. The mediator approach performs same task as the data warehouse but the only different is that it does not store the data itself [22]. The view mediated data integration is a framework used for solving data integration problems posed by structured data by using a unified view. The view mediated integration falls into three categories which includes Global As View (GAV), Local As View (LAV) and or Global or Local As View (GLAV). The proposed model will adopt the GLAV mediated data integration. In order for the mediator to decide what source data should be retrieved from and how to combine them to a unified view, the administrator of the view mediated data integration will have to specify the agreement between the local schema of each source and the global schema via mapping [23].

In virtual data integration, there are virtual schemas involved. For example, all information which are queried through the web app such as weather or social media are stored in a single database and this single database has a single schema. However, the collection of these information from the single database will be challenging due to all details being stored together and will lead to redundancy issues when extracting that information. Using virtual schema or virtual data integration will be the best option to provide solution to the challenge posed by traditional data integration. Virtual schemas differentiate extracted data for it to match perfectly well, it transforms every single query into appropriate queries with regards to different data sources and then it will combine the results obtained from different queries into one single query [24].

This paper [25] proposes a virtual data integration framework which consists of three processes. The processes include data integration process, inconsistency detection process and inconsistency resolution process. These processes are interfacing through storing the required data in a metadata which they called Meta Fusion Information Repository (MFIR). With this framework the data are stored in Fusion Meta Data in order to integrate, detect any inconsistency and to resolve the inconsistency involved in the process. Our proposed model Big Data Integration uses a virtual data integration process which will not involve data storage but promotes data virtualization. In other words it performs integration in real time based on the agreement between the data contributors and the data consumer. Each data contributors will provide the views that they are willing to share containing the information demanded by data consumers and the data consumers will only access the view when needed. Therefore, the data contributors are in-charge of their own data; they are responsible for updating the views of which the data contributors can access anytime. In this process data are left in their sources.

2.3.1 Challenges of Data Integration

The challenge with data integration falls on data storage ability of database, inadequate resources (that is the cost and lack of skilled experts who understands the new data), skilled professional who are now difficult to find since data integration requires high professionals who understand the model of data and which right tools to use [18]. Other challenge known is scalability which crops up when new information from numerous sources is integrated with

data from legacy systems and as a result influences the efficiency of legacy systems. This happens due to some system modification to fit the specification of new technologies. Another challenge is the ETL process as each data item passes through an ETL process, the transformation of huge data set will affect the storage ability of databases [18].

A research by [6] further explained that, there are three major challenges faced with data integration. One of which is Semantic Ambiguity where the form at which the data is stored in their sources are too broad to understand and these data formats are written differently in their different sources. The second challenge is the instance representation ambiguity, this is whereby an instance A might represent Airline1 in Airport1 and Instance A might be represented as Airfare in Airport2. Therefore, when the instances are represented differently from different sources, it will be difficult for integration. Lastly, data inconsistency is part of the challenge of data integration because one system may be out-dated, and the other system may have current date which may result into integrating data with diverse different date and time. Most especially when large data sets are involved, unstructured data resides in higher volume [163].

Another challenge of data integration is structural integration. This is related to the heterogeneity of a data model which is often related to legacy system. This legacy system known as out-of-date data cannot accept new requirements and technologies and this is because they are not managed by who understands it [7].

A researcher also pointed out that, the time and impact required to create the data source description and semantic mapping between the data source and the mediated schema is one major challenge in setting up a data integration application [78]. Other challenges of data integration are lack of data management expertise, unanticipated costs, uncertainty of data management, extracting value from data and bad data.

2.3.2 Big Data Integration Tools

TABLE 2: Big data integration tools and their features

Big Data Tools	Features of Big Data Tools
MapD Technologies	It is an Interactive Analytics at Scale It does Instant query and allows you to visually explore your data with the power of GPUs The company offers MapD Core, an in-memory, column store, and SQL relational database. It can be used in IoT, log analytics, retail and many more [26].
SAS	It is used for advanced analytics, multivariate analyses, business intelligence, data management, and predictive analytics. It adopts the use of ETL technologies, migrate data between database structures and provides virtual access to database structures [27].
SSIS	This is a Microsoft tools in SQL server which has the platform form for data integration. It is used to perform wide range of data migration tasks. It is used to solve complex business problem. It is also used for updating data warehouses, cleaning and mining data and managing data [28].

R	R is an integrated group of software facilities which is used for statistical computing and graphics. It provides wide range of statistical techniques which includes time-series analysis, linear and non-linear modelling. R programming language is used for data analysis by most data miners and statisticians [29].
Synscort	A data integration tool with high – performance join algorithm. It allows easy import of jobs from other platform Example: IBM data-stage. It has advantages in shortening the timeframe used in deployment and development. It utilizes I/O optimisation, parallel processing and dynamic environmental monitoring techniques [30]; [31].
Striim	This deals with wide range of fast data from in-stream processing and analytics, loading of big data and also as a storage environment. striim uses SQL –like languages. Striim software combines in real-time, performs other data processes like aggregations, filtering, transformation and masking [32].
Talend	It is a data integration product which provides performant, stands as an open-source set of tools and it integrates data from any business system in real-time. It supports Big Data /NoSQL, ETL for business intelligence and data warehousing, data synchronization, data migration, data sharing, and data services. It connects to database, cloud applications, OLAP applications, web services as well as data warehouses [33].
Jitterbit	Another data integration tool which addresses the cost and complexity challenges of data management, cloud applications and business processes. No coding is involved; it has graphical approach and therefore supports drag and drop to map data transformations [34].
Laiason	This tool supports Data Orchestration, Data Persistence and Data Visualization. It integrates applications, manages data with accessible APIs and allows data flow through customised interfaces. It supports Data Services, Cloud Services, Data Mapping, Data Transformation, Data Security, and Security [35].
Denodo	It is Data Virtualisation tools which offer high performance Data integration for big data, unstructured data sources and real-time data services. This software creates the possibilities of leaving all sources of data exactly where it is, store them across myriad heterogeneous systems, and to establish a virtual, “logical data lake” for accessing all the data. It also provides a unified single view of data [36].
Attunity	This is a software solution that allows access, sharing and distribution of data, as well as Big Data. It supports data replication, change data capture, data connectivity, enterprise file replication and managed-file-transfer [37].
Attivio	This supports both structure and semi structured data, unstructured data, Big Data, different databases, and it uses out-of-the-box connectors to relational databases, file content, XML and CSV data [38].
Dell Boomi AtomSphere	It is a drag-and-drop data integration process which uses a visual interface to configure application integrations. It also has data mapping tools, along with a library of application and technology connectors which you can build from simple to sophisticated integrations with exceptional speed. It supports wide variety of enterprise integration scenarios, including B2B, EDI and web services [39].

Action	It is a software solution for database integration which converts data from different formats, deploys complex application data integration scenario and integrate applications even in the cloud. It supports drag-and-drop links, Lifecycle Management, SOA Platform, Cloud-to-Cloud Computing Interchangeable and Reusable Metadata [40].
Adeptia	This is Data Integration tool that supports Any-to-Any Conversion, Graphical Data Mapper, Metadata-Driven, Web-Based UI, it is code-free, it supports Business User Access, Preconfigured Connections, Web Service API Publishing, Web Portals, and Customer On-boarding [41].
Alooma	This is a data integration tool for cloud data warehouse. It serves as a service platform which provides data scientists and data engineers the ability to integrate, cleanse, enrich and bring together data from various silos to any data warehouse [43].
Altova MapForce	It is an automated data integrator where free data integration codes are in Java, C# and C++ that means it doesn't support code writing. It uses REST web-services by calling it from within a mapping [42].
Oracle Data Integrator	This tool's data integration solutions provide a complete, open and integrated solution for building, deploying, and managing real-time data in an analytical environment. This tool also takes data integration to the next level and deliver extreme performance and scalability for all enterprise data movement and transformation needs. It is also easy to use [44].

Table 2 - gives an overview of each products or tools used in the process of data integration. There are some new products which outlines the need for data virtualization with the purposed of reducing too much data in the system. Examples of such include Denodo product, Altovia MapForce and Actian. Actian uses Restful services, it is a lightweight application which uses data-connect to provide hundreds of connectors to common application.

According to Gartner Denodo technology has been recognised for the second time as a challenger in 2019 Gartner Magic Quadrant in the aspect of data integration tools. In other words, among the data integration tools Denodo has been one of the best which has grew from 4.63% in 2018 to 12.05% in 2019 [62].

2.4 DATA WAREHOUSE

Data warehouse is the steady housing of data which is made available to data consumers in a comprehensive way and be used in a business context [45]. A data warehouse is a central repository for integrated information that originates from one or more sources. The data integrated from different sources can be structured data, semi-structured data and unstructured data. The concept and fundamental aim of data warehouse is to retrieve information using ETL tools and perform analysis using a multi-dimensional data model, where access is done by SQL with data analysis extensions and the condition of data it houses or analyses is historical and descriptive data [46]; [121]. Data warehouse technology consists of Data marts, Meta data, Data architecture and the ETL process. A data warehouse performs various tasks such as managing and enhancing customer relationships, reviewing and optimising logistics and operations, monitoring and managing corporate performance, performing forecasts of future growth, future needs and deliverables, and also cleansing and improving the quality of an

enterprise's data [47]. Data warehousing (DW) is a proper system which is used for reports and analysis and is widely considered an essential element for decision processes. In 1970s Bill Inmon was known as the father of DW and others (Barry Devlin, Ralph Kimball and Paul Murphy) developed a theory of data warehousing with good examples [48]. The analysis of large quantities of data collected from different sources without powerful tools is a great challenge, which has led to analysis of how data should be stored, integrated, managed and analysed. These requirements led to the need for data warehousing and data mining [49]. Decision support brings different requirements for database technology, compared to a traditional online transaction processing application. DW plays a crucial role in decision making by providing reliable and efficient tools to decision makers. The data warehouse integrates a wide range of heterogeneous data sources in multidimensional structures that support decision making [50]. Data warehousing applies ETL technology [50]; [48]. A traditional data warehouse uses the ETL process to extract data from different databases and combines it in a centralised form using a global schema which appears as a single database.

The Data warehousing architecture in **Figure 1** describes the process from data acquisition to data integration, to data repository, to analytics and finally to presenting. Data acquisition is controlled by software program used to acquire data from heterogeneous sources or hardware like sensors (detecting pollution from different location) and this data is taken from real-world to the hardware. Basically, data warehouse is like relational database which is used for analytical purposes. It is a centralized database where data extracted from multiple sources are stored together. Data repository refers to specific type of storage entities. It is like data mart which reserves a population of data isolated so it can be used for greater insight. They are like groups of databases except for various purposes. In the Traditional Data Warehousing, each of the database and software tools requires maintenance. A simulation from this research [149], shows that tradition data warehouse approach requires around 100 days' worth of maintenance to fix a system whereas data virtualisation requires 20 days' worth of fixing. Based on their comparison of stock and flow models, the researchers then clearly stated that Data Virtualisation is much better solution in terms of operational cost.

2.5 LOGICAL DATA WAREHOUSE

Logical data warehouse (LDW) is new data management architecture which is used for analysis. This approach combines the strength of traditional repository warehouse, alternative data management and access strategy [123]. This paper [124] explained LDW as a single view of data. The logical layer of the data warehouse delivers different techniques for viewing data both in warehouse store and across different organizations without transporting or transforming data. With logical data warehouse views are provided and these views act as an interface into different data and its sources [125]. Logical data warehouse is needed because organisations are not yet satisfied with the traditional data warehousing, enterprises are seeking for a better management of data like LDW because the traditional data warehouse is slow in process and it has also increased within end users' organisations [124]. With logical data warehousing different enterprise data will be treated as one singular data warehousing for large-scale information management.

With the use of data virtualisation, access is granted easily to data and federated data. Data virtualisation layers can initiate externally managed processes [124]. Element that forms the logical data warehousing are Repository management, Data Virtualisation, Distributed Processes, Auditing Statistics and performance evaluation services, Service Level Agreement (SLA), management, taxonomy or ontology Resolution and Metadata management [123]. Logical data warehouse also responds faster to your ever-changing analytics and business intelligence. Data virtualisation platform requires the ability to discover the data stored from different data sources, retrieve data from different data sources, define views or virtual tables, optimize federated query, cache data and fine-grained security [149]. One of the benefit of LDW from a research which was carried out for over three (3) years from Cisco Data virtualization shows that IT project cost avoidance is \$1,287,000, IT operating cost savings was 50% of over three years and there was an increase in end user productivity of \$3,834,000 over three years [150].

2.5.1 Virtual Views/ Virtual Tables

A view is a saved SQL query. It is a virtual table that executes SQL statements. A view provides up-to-date data. View permission allows a user to see the metadata of which the permission is granted [28]. Views can limit the amount of disclosure of the information in the main table to the public, with views multiple tables can be joined into a single virtual table. Views can appear as aggregate table meaning it can sum-up data and present a calculated result as part of the data; therefore, it hides the complexity of data. Query optimization execution is very important in virtual views or virtual tables since data is fetched from different data sources, which means data cleansing, data joining, and data transformation are all defined in virtual tables [149]

2.5.2 Systematic Research on Logical Data Warehouse

This section is to express the low value of research work in academia regarding the topic of Logical Data warehouse and its' associates. After search on different search engines such as Science direct, IEEE Xplore, without any year restriction, a key word Logical Data Warehouse was used and the number of results is 7,102 and on IEEE Xplore 130, with restriction from 2010 till date on IEEE Xplore total results was 70 out of the 70 results only 3 articles are related to logical data warehouse. With year restriction from 2018 to 2021 the result was 939. With the result so far, most of the title is non-related to logical data warehouse. A new key word Virtual Data Warehouse was used without any restrictions and the total number resulted to 6,630. With restrictions from year 2017 to 2020, the research article and reviewed articles resulted to 1,404. Virtual data integration was used on IEEE Xplore with restrictions from 2015 till date resulted to 776 articles which I randomly looked through these articles and out of 25 articles few articles relate to my topic of research.

TABLE 3: Search keywords with no year restrictions

Key word	Database search engine	No. of Results	No of related article
Logical data warehouse	Elsevier	7,108	
Virtual data warehouse	Elsevier	6,630	

TABLE 4: Search keywords with year restrictions

Keyword	D. Search Engine	Year restrictions	No. of Results	No. Related Article
Logical data warehouse	Elsevier	2018 - 2021	939	
Virtual data warehouse	Elsevier	2017 -2020 Research Article, Reviewed Article	1,404	

TABLE 5: Article title/ Abstract related to research?

Article Title	D. Search Engine	Related based on Abstract?	If not, Why
A data integration platform for patient-centred e-healthcare and clinical decision support	Elsevier	No	Because historical data is needed [95].
Evolutionary game theory approach to materialized view selection in data warehouses	Elsevier	No	More of query optimization [96].
Job flow management for virtualized resources of heterogeneous distributed computing environment	Elsevier	Yes	N/A [97]
BigDimETL with NoSQL Database	Elsevier	No	The research is about dimensional ETL to suit big data. It is not using a logical form. [94]
Logical query optimization for Cloudera Impala system	Elsevier	No	This research is focusing on the query processing challenges and proposed a method to solve the challenges.[93]
Tracing data warehouse design	Elsevier	No	This research focuses on designing an

lifecycle semantically			approach that traces decisions taken while building a data warehouse. [92]
SETL: A programmable semantic extract-transform-load framework for semantic data warehouses	Elsevier	No	This research described the use of programmable Semantic ETL (SETL) which will build on semantic web standards and tools. [91]
Efficient data access and performance improvement model for virtual data warehouse	Elsevier	YES	n/a [90]
Data Warehouse with Big Data Technology for Higher Education	Elsevier	No	This paper explained the benefit of using big data technology implemented in data warehouse on decision making support for university. [89]
The effects of database complexity on SQL query formulation	IEEE Xplore	No	This paper focused on the complexity in database design which has led to reduction in success rate of query transformation from student. [88]
DISERTO: Semantics-Based Tool for Automatic and Virtual Data Integration	IEEE Xplore	Yes	This paper focused the semantic, syntactic, and schematic heterogeneity of the data and proposed semantic virtual Data Integration tools which will aid in extracting relevant meta data and mapping metadata

Table 5: Outlines Different subject area relating to Logical date warehouse but very few contents contained in each article are related to subject matter of this research.

2.5.3 Logical Data Warehouse tools (Data Virtualization)

Data virtualization tools are qualified in abstracting data through a virtualized layer, they also integrate data from various sources and facilitate data manipulation. The tools supporting data virtualization are listed in **Table 6** below; the **Table 6** outlines the advantages of the data virtualization tools including their disadvantages.

TABLE 6: Explaining the different Data Virtualization tools

DV Tools	Features; Advantages and Disadvantages
SAP HANA	It is a fast and consistent ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) tools, data are stored in column based, it has great user interface. It can be used on cloud, on premises or on hybrid model. It uses in memory processing for better analytics based on live data. It also has disadvantages which are high cost of software and its' setup, lack of support in understanding the right product to choose, the applications are designed based on legacy database architecture which makes industry not taking full advantages of SAP HANA, lack of quality data [135]; [136].
Informatica PowerCentre	It is a tool that provides a unique end-to-end integration platform. It has a broad range of capability to integrate raw fragmented data from different sources. Some of the advantages are; it uses ETL to build Enterprise data warehouse, it provides different kinds of transformation techniques which can fit into various business needs, it allows easy integration with other application, it provides real-time data integration services. Disadvantages: Normalization are difficult to comprehend for new developers, the automation system has poor functionalities, one has to have the knowledge of shell scripting in order to do an implementation, it cannot handle huge amount of data and the processing period is very slow [139]; [140].
IBM BigInsights	This integrates Hadoop and Sparks together for a processing of any kind of data to be fast. It is an open source application that supports built on IBM open platform which provides complete distribution of Apache ecosystem component that are open source [141] [142].
AWS Glue	It is a serverless ETL tool, it converts raw data to parquet format, which is not available with other ETL tools, it converts huge sum of data without stress, and it is cost effective. Disadvantages: it is not developer friendly; it internally uses hadoop system which takes much time to run, it is not so easy to learn and implement and there are not enough materials to educate users [143]; [148].
Denodo	It consolidates multiple disparate data sources with single joins, it uses a RESTFUL endpoint to retrieve data in different response data formats, it connects to multiple disparate data sources and creates views on top of each, and it also has the ability in creating different data virtualization layer and connects data between data source databases. Disadvantages: the caching option needs improvement; query function and views writing are complex and hard to understand [36].
Oracle Virtualization	It is cost effective, it is open-source software, it has better performance, simple and fast, it virtualizes workloads and thereby reduces number of servers used. Disadvantages: Updates are applied manually, Licensing are expensive [146].

Data Virtuality	This made management much more efficient and effective, it takes short time to connect to different data sources, it provides a flexible virtual SQL layer, it has many connectors which have provided access to the full API and it can model and transform data with SQL, it has a built –in REST services. Disadvantages: it does not have enough restricted access to what users can see, using it requires those with experience and understanding of logical data warehousing design [137]; [138].
VMWare VClouid	It provides SLAs for all applications, it provides standard virtualization that companies utilize in their data centre, it does great technical support. Disadvantages: Poor performance on backup processes especially on very large job, it might be expensive to use and payment for services is hourly [145].
TIBCO data virtualization	The user interface is easy to use, it represents data as service, it sets up federated queries faster across heterogeneous sources. Disadvantages: Poor performance, means of optimising queries gets confusing to end users, it has complex environment especially in deployment of solutions [144].

2.6 BUSINESS ASPECT AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS (BIG DATA INTEGRATION AND DATA WAREHOUSE)

Data analytics deploy various tools and techniques for the purpose of collecting data, transforming, cleaning, classifying, and converting it into meaningful information, visualisation and reporting formats [63]. There are different stages that make up the lifecycle of Big Data analytics. These stages include the business case study, data identification, data extraction, data filtering, data cleansing and validation, data aggregation and representation, data analysis and data visualisation. Under these stages data integration and data warehousing are categorised. Data warehouse deals with organisation raw data from multiple sources, combines them (data) together into a centralised location, then, optimizes them for reporting and analysis. The combining and optimisation stage (that is the data integration stage) uses the ETL processes to copy these data from multiple sources, clean these data and load them into the data warehouse [64].

2.6.1 The benefits of data warehouse on businesses.

One of the benefit of data warehousing is for better decision making. When dealing with business, the main goal is to make a better business decision than your competitors. With proper decision making, using data warehousing in supporting decision making will affect marketing segmentation, inventory management, financial management and sales [73].

Data warehousing should be a benefit for quick and easy access to data. If data accessibility is easy and fast, it sets your business above your competitors. It is, therefore, important that businesses must consider the time taken in retrieving data from different or multiple sources.

Customers' data are being generated with great speed and this has led to data warehouse gathering information from multiple data sources at same time. These data being generated have different forms which demands converting them into a single and widely used format. This means that businesses using data warehouse must consider the data quality and data consistency. Hence, data needs to be accurate to make sound business decisions [73].

2.6.2 The challenges of data warehouse on businesses

Gartner states that poor data warehousing practise “undermines the organisation’s digital initiatives, weakens their competitive standing and sow customer’s distrust” [65];[66].

As business data becomes smarter, the numbers of data channel and volume have increased rapidly alongside with technological advancement and this has resulted more in difficulty in keeping track of information and storing information. Even though data warehouse has become common practise for many businesses, there are still challenges relating to it. Below are the challenges explained.

A user expectation in using data warehouse practise is to have better performance during the implementation. As more information is being added to the data warehouse, the performance decreases due to the increase of data volume, resulting in reduced speed and poor efficiency. As the volume of data increases, when adding data to data warehouse, the management system will have to work vigorously to find the specific information needed and then analyse it. This process alone leads to time consumption in businesses [67].

With regards to cost as being a challenge to businesses using data warehouse practice, setting up a data warehouse to build and manage a specific designed on-premises data centre requires a huge investment in the Information Technology (IT) resources. Due to the cost involved, some vendors offer data warehousing functions as a service (DWaaS) and can be accessible through internet connections. That has resulted in a new data warehouse concept which is cloud data warehousing. Managing a data warehouse in the cloud is a new set of challenges on its own and so organisations need to understand these challenges relating to cloud DW before making the choice of using it. With cloud-based data warehousing, the cost structure is very different from how one would pay for standard servers in an on-premises data centre [60]; [21].

Another challenge faced by business is skills shortage. Using cloud-based data warehouse for example, many businesses see a barrier in adopting it due to lack of resources and skilled expertise. Businesses tend to stick to traditional data warehouse or old practices because when they evaluate the cost involved in hiring an expert who understands the architecture, technical understanding of data integration in the cloud system and in-depth understanding of cloud security and data governance, it is realised that it is expensive [68].

As a business owner, it is a challenge to choose the right type of warehouse that will suit your business requirements. There are varieties of warehouse types available in the market but before making the choice, one needs an expert that will understand the business requirements and data to choose the right warehouse types for the specific goal. Understanding the business data needs is another challenge on its’ own. Data warehouse operates with the information one supplies to it. So then, if wrong information is being supplied to it, the result will be inaccurate thereby leading to poor quality of data. One needs to understand the data and the business needs at the initial stage in order to have a better-quality result [67].

2.7 DATA SECURITY

Data warehouses are the organisation’s most valuable assets in business information and that makes it a target for attackers. With the nature of data warehouse queries and increasing volume of data, most existing data security solutions are now inefficient [69]. Security concerns on

data warehouse is one of the major challenges that organisations face, and this is because business data warehouses are usually very large systems, comprises of different data owners with varying security needs. Recently, data warehouse has gone through different technological changes which has resulted in the security strategies concerns as well [70]. The basic requirements for security are applications to prevent unauthorised access to data, system must keep records of all activities done by its users, data must be available to the right user at the right time and the applications must not be susceptible to data theft by hackers. Security policies are directly attached to views, tables and synonyms and are applied automatically whenever a user accesses data. By attaching SQL statements with a predicate, virtual private database limits access to data at the row level. It allows multiple users to have direct access securely to critical data within a single database server [71]; [72]. Security failures also fall on customers' fault. Most cloud providers have provided strict security features which tend to be difficult for attackers to penetrate, but the problem of the security failures come from customers' fault. Gartner predicted that by 2020, 95% of cloud security failures will be from customers' fault [68].

When organisation data is consolidated into one large data warehouse, it is very important that sensitive data does not fall into the wrong hands. Organisations struggle with strict access control to information and so in many cases they protect only each front-end application. Maintenance of this implementation is costly and risk-prone because users have access to the database itself through SQL *Plus or a reporting tool and that makes access control built on application inefficient [71]. There are different approaches to security solutions on data warehouse which was proposed by some researchers [69]; [70]. One of the techniques is the Queries Over Encrypted Database. This technique was suggested as a solution to security challenges but since the event of DAS (Database as a Service) over the cloud, the techniques became inefficient. Other techniques are the Adaptive Mandatory Access Control Based OLAP, OLAP Security Design, Metadata Based Security Model (this technique provides access based on information about security objects and subjects which are stored as metadata), Unified Modelling Language (UML) Based Secure Data warehouse, XML Based Secure Data warehouse and Model Driven Architecture (MDA) Based Secure Data warehouse. Other solutions proposed by these researchers [69] are Preventive Data Security Solutions and Reactive Data Security Solutions. Preventive solution technique prevents and protects data in advance of attacks. Data masking is a preventive technique used in avoiding disclosure of data. Encryption is an advanced method of data masking in database management system. Due to the increased in sophisticated attack and internal theft, traditional preventive method is not good enough to protect data and that has resulted to the development of reactive data security techniques. Examples of reactive techniques are fault-tolerance, intrusion detection, auto-repair and auto-recovery. In reactive method, a hardware approach used is the RAID architecture and organisations tend to optimise cost which led to implementing data warehouse in low-cost commodity computers which uses only one disk and has resulted to RAID technology no longer an option. Other reactive techniques are oracle RAC, Aster Data, Hamming Codes, Mapping of bad blocks and Replication. Replication techniques have been an issue due to increase in volume of data and storage size issue [69].

2.8 SERVICE LEVEL AGREEMENT (SLAs)

A Service level agreement is a contract that is between two or more parties that is agreed on a specific service provided. The agreement should specify accepted or unaccepted service levels that falls between the data provider and the data consumers. The mode of SLA can be discussed or formalized based on circumstances. The benefits and objectives of SLA are for (i) mutual agreed standard, (ii) a better communication, (iii) guards against expectation creep and monitor quality of service, (iv) gauging service effectiveness [58]; [59].

The figure 3 below shows the SLA initiation cycle.

Figure 3: The SLA initialization cycle

Source: [77]

2.8.1 Issues Related to SLAs

The customer and contributor's relationship in the provision of services often includes guarantees of performance in order to gain confidence and these guarantees take the form of SLAs. There are some common issues regarding to SLAs policies that affect some scenarios such as a new policy not being displayed, a newly applied SLA executing additional breach events, and SLAs being applied only to some contracts. Sometimes, we observe that the absence of a service specification by a customer forces the SLA to act as specification whereas the main purpose of using SLAs is to provide a safety net in the customer and supplier relationship. SLAs should clearly define the limit of acceptable service but in some cases, SLAs appears to be "we guarantee 100% availability" which is clearly unachievable [74]. There are negotiations in relation to SLAs first discovering the important characteristics of the service; and then signing a clear agreement on the right and obligations of both the contributors and the client [75]. Rapid changes to business requirements are also issues with SLAs especially with the pace of change in technologies and business models [76]. Also, frequent updates may lead to performance delays in data exchange between service contributors and customers if the information depth of SLAs is unbounded [77]. Another research paper stated that SLA semantics and structural heterogeneity poses a challenge due to SLAs template comparison being complicated and thereby hinder any attempt to efficiently manipulate itself [77].

2.8.2 Benefits of using SLA

Semantic ambiguity and alignment which was stated earlier as challenges in data integration can be solved using SLAs between the data contributors and the customer. If the data consumer requests some data from different data contributors, the suppliers then send their data often with a different data format. The customer then tends to use a transformation process (from ETL) to transform the data received from different data sources to the format he wants to work with. Using the transformation method, it is hard because it may involve a lot of programming and time consuming, also, the customer may not know much about the data that needed to be transformed [19]. Negotiating an SLA allows the customer to have discussions with the data suppliers, enabling him a permission to understand the meaning of the data. The customer can or may also have an agreement with each of the data suppliers and one of the agreements may focus on the formats at which this data should be sent over or be accessed [77]. Therefore, using SLA can reduce data mismatch and may be able to meet the customer's business requirements.

2.9 GAPS IN KNOWLEDGE

From the above literature review, we can see that ETL techniques are widely used in the processes of data warehousing. However, ETL have a limitation in such that every-time new data sources are introduced, programmers must re-write a script that will suit each data sources. Programmers will continue to update ETL script to accommodate every new data source, and that is unsustainable. Semantic ambiguity and misalignment need to be overcome during the process of data migration. The migration of data process which is performed by most data integration tools during the process of data integration, poses a challenge because of the responsibility for GDPR is very blurred. It is observed that logical data warehouses are not widely used now, and this may be because it involves a lot of programming. It is not known whether businesses considered logical data warehouse in the aspect of data integration. The areas for research are to consider whether logical data warehouses would provide an easier route to data integration than ETL.

2.10 SUMMARY

This chapter presents a general review on the basic concept of data integration, data warehousing, big data, and logical data warehouse. The chapter also discussed the challenges related to big data and data integration with regards volume, variety, and velocity, and presents the combined challenges of big data and data integration to be big data integration. The chapter reviewed the traditional data warehousing and pointed out the reasons why organizations are not satisfied with it, explaining the logical data warehousing which is the new approach in data management. The work also pointed out the heavy computational cost and complexity involve when some Big Data challenges such as Volume and Variety are combined in data warehousing challenges. It also highlighted the cost of maintenance especially when third-party is involve in managing data source's data. The research also explains what logical data warehouse and the different tools which adopt it. Finally, the research presents a brief explanation of SLAs (which was used as part of the proposed framework) with its benefits and challenges related to it. With the literature review relating the research questions in section 1.3, implementing the research objectives will answer the research questions.

In the next chapter, we will outline the overview of this approach used in the research.

CHAPTER 3: PROPOSED APPROACH TO ACHIEVING LOGICAL DATA WAREHOUSE

3.1 OVERVIEW

This chapter focuses on the approach of achieving the data virtualisations using the HTTP and Representational State Transfer (REST) mechanism. The HTTP and REST mechanism acts as webservice in this approach. The REST concepts can be an Application Program Interface (API) which act as the mediator, as means of communication between different databases from different sources. This approach is similar to the RESTView techniques and RESTif as webservice. This chapter also gives a brief explanation of the application of RESTif techniques which can apply to other Database Management System (DBMS) including Microsoft SQL and not only on Pyrrro DB, explaining the benefits of RESTView techniques and its limitations. The proposed framework aimed to achieve a logical data warehouse in which specific data can be accessed on demand from individual databases, by sending queries to the data contributor's database through a Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and Representational State Transfer (REST) interface. The REST interface acts as a mediator between the data sources and the consumers' data warehouse where the process of integration is done [52]. In the global database, the local data source is represented using a view that specifies a REST URL. Using the query transformation mechanisms, it can transform global queries against the views created by data contributors to specific aggregated and filtered queries to the sources of the data. RESTView technique a similar approach is one of the technologies that make it possible to perform data integration without the need of copying the whole data from source database to destination database. If RESTView is implemented within the global DBMS, any of its database or data integration tools would be able to request data through automatically constructed aggregated and filtered SQL query statements, accessing the source databases using HTTP. The query sent by the data consumer (client) in the global environment is answered by specific selected aggregated information that is obtained from appropriate data sources only when required. The mechanism assumes that URL provided by the data source is based on a service level agreement between the data contributor and the global system, under which the global system is given secure access to the specific data specified in the view. This means that the overall volume of data that needs to be transferred from the data sources to the global system can be kept to a minimum. Under the conditions of "velocity" outlined in the introduction, this represents an enormous saving, as any item of real-time data is supplied only when required to meet a certain request from a client of the global system.

3.1.1 The Concept of REST

Representational State Transfer (REST) is a web design concept. It provides standard steps on how it should be used in developing web applications. REST is associated with HTTP. The aim of REST is to create a single or general interface whereby applications share the same convention [53]. This means that one application knows how to communicate to all other application and vice versa. It provides independent deployment of component. This explains further that, if one REST interface is implemented on any application, you can always implement and deploy the REST interface without rewriting or modifying existing ones. One can make an application into a REST-like application by just using or adding a REST interface. REST reduces interaction latency (time delay) by using intermediary components [54]. REST over HTTP is implemented in terms of request and response. When used for data integration, both requests and responses can contain indications of the representation of the resource. The

REST representation contained in the response is the status of a resource. REST supports updating of a resource and some resources may allow this. REST provides a suitable integration technique for information services and many REST interfaces today use sends JSON format for responses. The verbs (GET, POST, PUT, DELETE) used in REST were incorporated in HTTP1.1 although web browsers continue to use the HTTP 1.0 subset.

3.1.2 The Previous Work – RESTView

What is RESTView Technology?

The RESTView technology requires a small extension to SQL syntax [52]. SQL syntax can define what a view is but does not have the ability to call a view ‘as get’ using HTTP. Whereas, with RESTView technology, the syntax has been extended to include the possibility of calling a view ‘as get’. RESTView can be the target of a large set of SQL queries that can automatically filter, aggregate, or join data provided as views by the remote databases. With ordinary query statements, one has to perform the select statement to call the views and get the rows on the current database. While with RESTView, a query will result in one or more HTTP requests on remote databases. RESTView associates the view with a URL but one should not request all information in the URL; instead, the automatic query generator will transform the HTTP request to apply the filtering and aggregation that defines the information requested. The RESTView definition defines the global view ‘as get’ URL and the URL are defined according to the contributors.

With this SQL extension, it is often the case that no further programming will be needed to access data from remote views. RESTView is a technology for data integration which can achieve a logical data warehouse because it avoids the copying data from source database to destination database. It defines a view as an ‘HTTP get’ and does not store remote data in the logical database. The requirements for the data integration using RESTView are the agreed views and the URLs provided by the contributors.

RESTView views the data on the remote database source, selects the specific information needed and performs data transformation and data filtering and returns data (result) to the clients’ database. RESTView uses RESTif as a web-service to access the view provided by the contributors. With this technology, Pyrrho database now adopts RESTView and will be a logical database because it sees the data provided as “as get” but does not copy all data [55].

Figure 6 shows part of the RESTView technology that has and uses RESTif. The Pyrrho database in **Figure 6** is a logical database which is contacting RESTif. RESTView defines a view as HTTP GET. This means that there is a logical database on Pyrrho which calls the view as ‘get it from its source’. The HTTP GET is coming from Pyrrho and contacting RESTif. With RESTView, the remote data contributor provides a view, RESTView accesses the view of the data contributor’s database using RESTif. RESTif is just the mediator using REST interface such as HTTP to access directly to the views of each databases, serving as web-services.

Figure 6 –RESTif as Web-services

3.1.2.1 RESTif Mechanism

RESTif mechanism is a little application which sits on database server. It acts as a mediator between the contributors' database and client database. This little application can be applied on any database (MySQL, SQL server, Oracle) and it is a small webservice which targets the differences between different DBMSs. This is good to be implemented because it does not need any configuration whereas other web-services perform some recompilation for different databases to work together. It is portable to use, and it is for simplicity on data collection. RESTif is an application as little as 19kb; it also wraps groups of SQL statement into transactions. Figure 7 describes how RESTif serves as web-service which allows clients' database or device to access DBMS over HTTP.

Figure 7 – Process of RESTif as web-services

When using RESTif mechanism, there will be certain Service levels of agreement between the data contributors and the data consumer (Client) and after the agreement is successful the views will be provided based on SLA. RESTif mechanism does not reduce the amount of data it only provided access to database as web-services. Using the SLA reduces the access to too many personal data. Therefore, setting up service level agreement only gives permission access to only the data that the data contributors want the data consumer (client) to have access to. Organisation can use RESTif mechanism alone without RESTView and the process is almost as similar but RESTView provide a logical database and deals with views while RESTif can

access the databases. For data security purpose, the data contributor can decide to provide a view to the data consumer (client) and give access permission to those views only.

The main difference between RESTif and other database services is that it uses HTTP which makes it easier to interface with data integration. RESTif mechanism is a way of getting the remote data contributor's database to respond to HTTP to be as a web-server. That is, RESTif mechanism provides a way of bringing database services into the category of web-services which contributes to data integration. For example, if a business decides to increase the amount of the integration they got between things, one way of improving this is the web-services access to the data.

3.1.2.2 RESTif mechanism as Web-services

RESTif as micro-services is an independent platform that communicates with other systems or mechanism without any centralised control. Its communication is over message protocol like HTTP concept and uses independent services as web-services where access is done through HTTP. The difference between RESTif and other micro-services is that with RESTif one can easily access the views or data through http concept by providing a direct access to database with the provided SQL statement while micro-services do not. RESTif as web-services act as an intermediary between the clients' database and contributor's database. RESTif acts as web-service allowing one to access data through http service. RESTif acts as web-services by allowing the 'get' to perform SQL statement then click get to this address and it will return data without any parameters. RESTif provides direct access to database with the provided SQL statement. It is advisable or left for the contributors to create a view from the database they've got and grant access permission to the client so that the client will access the views only rather than the whole database. With this practise organisation will restrict access to data.

3.1.3 Using RESTif Concept as web-services on Microsoft SQL Server

As mentioned earlier, RESTif concepts can operate on any database. The use of RESTif on Microsoft SQL Server is one example. Before the RESTif application can operate on any DBMS, the client must configure the security logins on Microsoft SQL management studio giving it the username and password. Then, next is to run the RestifS.exe on your system with no configuration needed and run also the RESTClient.exe where one can input the URL given to them by the data contributors with the name of the view or table on it and with the security login credentials. The process will extract the exact information on request using the aggregated filtered SQL queries and the data appears in JSON / XML format. Note that, the client cannot demand all data that are created in the views by the data contributors because he cannot see what has been provided. The views which are provided are based on the level of service agreement.

Figure 8 – Application of RESTif as Web-services on Microsoft SQL Server

3.1.4 What are the benefit of RESTView Technology Using RESTif?

Using RESTView technology in which Pyrrho database has adopted, for any actual request expressed in SQL pyrrho DB automatically calculates what SQL statement to send to the contributor. Using RESTView technology, it controls and minimizes the amount of data requested. Which means that, if other databases like MySQL or Oracle adopts this technology, it can automatically calculate what SQL statement to send to the contributor. Using RESTView technology provides a logical data warehouse. This means that data will be used and not be stored. There are transaction logs that will aid in tracking or monitoring data transactions, but logical data warehouse will treat the database as virtual memory. With Rest-view the remote contributor provides a view, rest-view accesses the view with RESTif. RESTif is not about a view just the http access directly to database. It is advisable or left for the contributors to create a view from the database they've got and grant access permission to the client so that the client will access the views only rather than the whole database.

RESTView be a technology while RESTif is a fixed application, that is simple and portable. Any organization adopting RESTif will construct some SQL statement or can give a URL to the client whereby the content in the URL specified an entity in the database. While using RESTView technology Pyrrho DB automatically calculates what SQL statement to send to the contributor: using RESTview, SQL statements process and send transformed query through RESTif. RESTif sits on the same machine as database server.

3.1.5 Who should Adopt RESTView technology and other Data Virtualisation technology?

With regards to RESTView, Pyrrho database uses the technology. Other DBMS can adopt RESTView technology, but what it requires is applying the syntax 'as get' extension to the SQL syntax. The syntax extension alone cannot achieve a logical data warehouse and therefore,

the second requirement is applying query transformation (this is also known as query aggregation) and query filtering. Using the syntax extension only can still retrieve all information provided in the views which still presents ETL process but when query transformation and query filtering is applied to the syntax extension, it will minimize the data returned.

With respect to the data contributors' database and clients' database, the regulatory bodies (clients) for example, which request for data need data virtualisation technology to be applied on their DBMS. The data contributors do not necessarily need to apply data virtualisation technology on their DBMS, they can adopt RESTif or web-services for the regulatory bodies (client) to access their database through HTTP interface. Notwithstanding, if the data contributors use other technology that provides an HTTP interface other than RESTif, then the process of integration will be viable. The basic need for the integration to be successful without copying is for the client to access the contributors' database via HTTP interface and for the process of integration to be done without obtaining all information from the source.

3.2 LOGICAL DATA WAREHOUSE

Logical data warehouse provides and uses virtual views as an interface to disparate data sources. It is an architectural layer that provides several means for viewing data in their warehouse. This architectural layer combines the strength of physical data warehouse with alternative data management techniques. The logical data warehouse complements the traditional data warehouse with certain techniques that extract and transform data in real-time. The logical architectural layer sits on top of organization's data warehouse. The user uses the virtual views (provided by the logical data warehouse) to fetch data from different sources without having knowledge of where the data is stored, where joins are being performed between data sets or what structures are the data sources defined. The technology used for logical data warehouse process is data virtualization, which allows users to only see what they need to see and when.

3.2.1 Benefit of Logical Data Warehouse to Organisational Sectors

- Using logical data warehouse allows data consumer to only see the information they need to see and work with.
- Also, the data owners are in-charge of their data including updates and data maintenance.
- The logical layer makes data fresher and in real-time.
- Instead of waiting for the ETL jobs to run within the data warehouse and updates records, the structure of the delivered data is created at run time without the need of data limited to a pre-built structure of data warehouse.
- Logical data warehouse federates SQL queries across various disparate data sources (the different data sources may be in cloud, an operational data store in Relational Database Management System, big data or unstructured reports.)
- It uses logical layer to create capabilities of the Enterprise Data Warehouse (EDW) by providing Business Intelligence total complete view of data by allowing together the physical and virtual layers to serve as the single source of truth.

- Another benefit is data can be accessed while being generated. This reduces dependencies on recurring batch oriented ETL [85].

3.2.2 What is the mediation between different data sources that is proposed?

Micro-services are an architectural style that construct a system as a collection of loosely coupled services, and it is a small autonomous service that is independently deployed with one single purpose. It is adopted by many organisations because it is of great advantage for single delivery. The aim of micro-services is to structure software system as sets of small services which can be deployed on different platform processing independently as well as communicating with other systems or mechanism without any centralised control [56]. Micro-services communicate over message protocol like HTTP and REST and can provide their functions to other services through an API. Micro-services use independent services as web-services where access is done through http. On the other hand, a web-service is a piece of software which provides basic means of exchange of information between different software applications, like making itself available over the internet. Web services are flexible; they allow communication between two or three different platforms. Web-services are built on open standards like HTTP, Java and XML. But the main component that makes a web-service platform is the combination of XML and HTTP.

Web-services architecture consists of service provider, service registry and service requester [57]. The basic process of web service is; both parties are known to each other, they have a service level of agreement on what semantics that both the requester system and contributor system can communicate, and lastly is the interaction between the contributor's system and requester's system. [57]. According to World Wide Web Consortium (2017), the World Wide Web operates as a networked information system where communications are exchange through a protocol that uses URLs. He explained further that, there is more constrained architecture which is more reliable for web-services. This architecture is REST, REST provides a uniform interface semantics that enables the 'create, delete, retrieve, and update' action and manipulate resources by an exchange of representation.

The mediation between different data sources is the web-service that is the API. The URL will be provided by the different data owners. The URL will contain the access details that can call the data in the views. Views provided by the data owners are supported or governed by SLAs. How does this process work is, the different data owners (care homes data source, NHS data source, PPE data source, coronavirus data source) agrees with regulatory body (department of health) that a particular information would be required from their database, the specific information would be listed and detailed by the regulatory body and the format the information should appear, and what the information is intended for use and how it will be used and how often the data will be accessed and how often the data should be updated. The data owners will then agree on what information they are willing to share.

Logical data warehouse is not for all industries. There are some organizations (like healthcare sectors, financial sectors, environmental sector) that depend on historical data to perform analytics in search for trends and predictions purposes. Different scenario where logical data warehouse can work... Logical data warehouse can be applied to certain sectors as Financial sector, health sector, educational sector, political sector, transportation sector, environmental sector, regulatory bodies such as Ofqual (the Office of Qualification and Examination Regulation), Ofsted (the Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills), OfS

(Office for Students), Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), Financial Reporting Council, Payment System Regulator (PSR), the Office for Professional Body Anti-Money Laundry Supervision (OPBAS), Environment Agency (EA), Natural Resources Wales (NRW), Northern Ireland Environment Agency (NIEA), Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), NHS Improvement, World Health Organization (WHO), Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC), Medicine and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA), Care Quality Commission (CQC), Regulator for Social Housing, Scottish Housing Regulator, Civil Aviation Authority(CAA), Department for Transportation (Dft), the Water Services Regulation Authority (Ofwat), Office of the Gas and Electricity Market (Ofgem), Food Standards Agency. The department for transportation (Dft) for example, works with different agencies and public bodies (24 in numbers) to support the transport networks and provide good travelling around the country.

3.3 THE RESEARCH PROPOSED MODEL/ APPROACH.

3.3.1 Overview

In this section, the research work describes ach process involved in achieving data virtualisation. This section also explains brief different terminology used in the proposed framework.

Views: A view is a saved SQL query. It is a virtual table that executes SQL statements. A view provides up-to-date data [28]. Views can limit the amount of disclosure of the information in the main table to the public, with views multiple tables can be joined into a single virtual table.

API: This stands for Application Programming Interface. APIs are set of functions or procedures or programming interface which enables communication between software products or two applications.

SQL Stored Procedure (SP): SP are prepared SQL codes or statement that are stored with an assigned name and are reusable, parameters can be passed to a SP and the SP acts based on the parameter values that is passed.

Data Contributors: these are the data owners that provide access to their databases based on SLA.

Data Consumers: They are the client that request for specific data from different source data owners

Figure 1 in 2.3 shows how a global database can provide many different analytics-based presentations while Figure 4 below explains the proposed method for data integration (data virtualisation), how specific report will be generated by aggregated filtered request to the data sources.

Figure 4 – The proposed model architecture

The **Figure 4** in 3.1.1 shows data coming from individual **Data Sources** (Data source M, Data source L and Data source B) with their views provided,

On the Logical Data Warehouse tile, the data is retrieved when API communicates with source database with URLs available, this data is retrieved in XML format, the web application is designed to convert this retrieved data in XML formats to tables and passes the table and the written aggregated SQL script to Stored Procedure (SP), the SP process the tables and the SQL scripts

On the Results and presentation tile, the result is then presented on webpage in a readable format that was designed by the data consumer.

Figure 5 below shows the flow diagram of the proposed model of big data integration process. This mechanism assumes the start of the framework which is the negotiation and the agreement between the data contributor (K) and the data consumer (B), If agreement is settled K creates a view of data required or requested by B and provides a URL to that database. B accesses the view using the access details and URL provided and retrieves information needed at the time in XML or JASON format. The data consumer has web application already created that the data retrieves appear and then transforms the XML formats to table formats designed in web engine in which the report is presented in that format.

Figure 5– The Flow Chart of the proposed model

3.3.2 Service Level Agreement (SLA)

A Service level agreement is a contract that is between two or more parties that is agreed on a specific service provided. The agreement may be accepted or unaccepted service level that falls between the data provider and the data consumers. The mode of SLA can be discussed or formalized and is based on specific circumstances. The benefits and objectives of SLA are for (i) mutual agreed standard, (ii) a better communication, (iii) guards against expectation creep and monitor quality of service, (iv) gauging service effectiveness [58]; [59].

In this thesis, the items involved in the SLA between the data contributors and the data consumers are as follows;

- A) Agreed mode of data access: - Data contributors are expected to provide a view from their own database and also provide a login details that only the data consumers will use to get access to the views provided.
- B) Data format or Table format: - Data consumers will provide a specific format that the views or table should be arranged on to the different data contributors for easy access and to reduce complexity and ambiguity. Each party needs to agree on the meaning of each data provided.
- C) The information required: - The data consumer will propose the kind of information that is requested from each data contributors and the data contributors will propose the amount of information they are willing to share and both parties will agree on one ground.
- D) URL's: - The data consumer will require a web form in this research as web-services to access the data provided by data contributors. Any of both parties will agree on who to create web-services.
- E) Data Update: - Both parties will agree on when data updates should occur or if data can be in real-time and data consumers can access it in real-time.
- F) Data usage
- G) Data confidentiality

The data contributors (data owners) will be in-charge of their data in terms of data quality, data efficiency, data security and many more. In this proposed model there are no rooms for storing data since it is in virtual or logical form and therefore, there there will be less concerns about time limits of data usage and destruction of the data about what time limit to use the data obtained and when should the data be destroyed.

3.3.3 How logical data warehouse can be a solution to some of the v's of big data

Volume: - Virtual data integration or data virtualisation (LDW) is a solution to data volume as its process uses an abstraction layer to provide a unified view of disparate data sources leaving data at their various data sources. Since data are not moved across from source database to destination database, then, there is a possibility of reduced data volume.

Velocity: - How data velocity is improved using logical data warehouse process? Since data virtualization uses a unified virtual data layer which is classified as lightweight and a flexible architecture then, it delivers data to application faster. This architecture does not encourage data moving across from one end to another, therefore the speed of the data movement is managed here. The benefit of using data virtualization is the presence of the additional layer on top of traditional data warehouse which provides fast and reliable access to data [86]. This means that data velocity is more efficient in this virtual data integration architecture.

Variety: - Data variety is referred to as different type of data from different sources [13]. Using logical data warehouse techniques, deploying data virtualization involves data coming from different data owners to be in an agreed format. This means that the data consumer (example: regulatory bodies) will have an agreement between different data owners (examples: National Health Service NHS, Army Public health centre, Administration for Children and Family) on the agreed format in which these data will appear in their different data sources. This agreement is known as Service Level Agreement (SLA).

3.4 SUMMARY

At the end of this chapter, it shows that previous work has been done in achieving data virtualisation techniques. This chapter described the previous work and its different approach it adopts. In this chapter, my framework adopted the REST concept as webservice for communication between databases or data sources. This section also described how SLAs is designed and the agreements involved that will help achieve the research framework.

CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY AND CASE STUDY

4.1 OVERVIEW

Based on the gaps in knowledge stated in 2.9, the research work aimed to design a novel data integration technique that will be efficient with less programming involved. This thesis also provided a model where data warehousing can be performed virtually and thereby, reducing the copy of data, promoting easy access of data, and reducing data semantic mismatch. With regards to the process of access to data, especially data required by government or regulatory bodies from private or public organisations (for example, data from the Universities, maybe to perform certain analysis), cannot be easily accessed. With the proposed model of data integration, performing data warehouse virtually will open gates for data to be effectively accessible by adhering to the SLA between parties. The service level agreement (SLA) allows organisations to control which data is accessible using any data virtualisation tools such as RESTView technology, the data formats and the amount of information required. Also, one does not need to place a call or email for information from different data contributor once SLA is involved and specific data created as views can be accessible remotely using webservices such RESTif or through API at any time based on the login credentials provided by the data contributors.

The research design and methodology used in this research is categorised into Qualitative approach and Prototype Implementation of proposal. Both approaches are required to answer the research questions. The qualitative approach used is intended to get the common analytical tools adopted by organisations and to obtain common challenges faced by current tools used. Whereas the prototype implementation is to experiment and describe how data volume can be reduced and to show the importance of SLAs.

4.2 QUALITATIVE APPROACH

This approach was designed as a questionnaire or/and telephone interview based on the convenience of the participant. With the consent form sent, the participant chooses which method best suit them to participate. Some participant answered the questionnaire sent while some request for telephone interview for further clarification.

In order to achieve the purpose for this research interview questionnaire, the researcher aimed for ten to twelve (10 - 12) responses from participant but received five (5). With the responses received, further telephone interview was conducted on two (2) participants, the researcher analysed the results and grouped them based on their similarities and their business case study and suggested a better approach that also suits their business case requirements. With the 5 responses, the researcher didn't push further to acquire the desired quantity as the research work is not completing as PhD research as per initial plans, so this work then did some analysis based on the 5 responses.

In the Qualitative approach, the interview questions were designed in order to answer the research questions. The participants were contacted by the researcher based on certain reasons and criteria. The criteria for choosing these participants are as follows;

- ❖ Based on the nature of their business if it involves Analysis,
- ❖ Reporting,
- ❖ Prediction,
- ❖ Statistics,

- ❖ Decision making and many more

With these criteria, data integration is involved. Data warehousing may not necessarily be involved but integration of data from different data sources are obviously involved.

The ethical application was submitted, and it was approved. The researcher has contacted various participants, the researcher needs a dozen of response in order to analyse their response and draw out observations but there are five (5) responses yet.

4.2.1 Ethical consideration

In the qualitative approach, interviews were conducted via email based on the participant choice. Ethical consideration is therefore very important at this stage of the research work and must be carried out.

The confidentiality and anonymity of each data collection tools would be assured, the participant was informed the purpose and implication of what they are to do, how the researcher would use their data in the given period of research, and consent form was provided for the participant to confirm their choices.

The consent form and the constructed interview questions were prepared and sent out; the researcher received the ethical approval to make the next move. The ethical application has been approved and contacts were made.

The ethical application comprises of the following;

- ❖ Consent Form
- ❖ Participant Information Sheet and
- ❖ The Interview Questions.

After the approval of the Ethical Application, contacts have been made to various firms including

- ❖ Business Intelligence department in UWS Paisley campus
- ❖ Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA)
- ❖ Renfrewshire Council
- ❖ Department for Education
- ❖ Department for Transport (Bus Statistics)
- ❖ Department for Transportation (Road Traffic statistics team)
- ❖ Department for Transport (Vehicles & Admin Statistics team)
- ❖ NHS Digital
- ❖ Department for Transport (Road Congestion Statistics)
- ❖ Department for Transport (Aviation Statistics)
- ❖ Department for Transport (Developing-Data-Unit)
- ❖ Chevron
- ❖ Azzurro Associates
- ❖ Phusion IM
- ❖ Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA)
- ❖ World Health Organisation (WHO)
- ❖ Department for Transport (Maritime Statistics)

- ❖ Department for Transport (rail Statistics)
- ❖ Department for Transport (environment Statistics)
- ❖ Department for Transport (Research Strategy)
- ❖ Ofsted
- ❖ Transport Api
- ❖ Trusted Data, On Demand (DOORDA)
- ❖ MIME Consulting
- ❖ Kognitio
- ❖ Swirrl

TABLE 7: Outlining the different participant that was contacted with their response and reasons

Participants	Response	Reasons
Business Intelligence department in UWS Paisley campus	Participated	N/A
Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA)	Participated	N/A
Renfrewshire Council	No Response	N/A
Department for Education	Unable to Participate	Busy time for the department due to the conservative party leadership change and cabinet reshuffle.
Department for Transport (Bus Statistics)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transportation (Road Traffic statistics team)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transport (Vehicles & Admin Statistics team)	Unable to participate	Due to limited resources
NHS Digital	Unable to participate	The information requested by researcher is what they are not prepared to put into the public
Department for Transport (Road Congestion Statistics)	Participated	N/A
Department for Transport (Aviation Statistics)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transport (Developing-Data-Unit)	Unable to Participate	They are new team and most of the questions asked by the researcher

		will require much effort.
Chevron	Participated	N/A
Azzurro Associates	Participated	N/A
Phusion IM	No Response	N/A
Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA)	No Response	N/A
World Health Organisation (WHO)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transport (Maritime Statistics)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transport (rail Statistics)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transport (environment Statistics)	No Response	N/A
Department for Transport (Research Strategy)	No Response	N/A
Ofsted	No Response	N/A
Transport Api	No Response	N/A
Trusted Data, On Demand (DOORDA)	No Response	N/A
MIME Consulting	No Response	N/A
Kognitio	No Response	N/A
Swirrl	No Response	N/A

4.2.2 Analysing the Participant Response to Interview Questions

The interview questions were designed in such a way that it can answer the research questions which are

What are the problems associated when tools such as ETL precede big data analytics?

Below are the interview questions designed.

QUESTION 1

Are there business case data requirements in your organisation that may require data integration? If YES, what technology or tools do you adopt in the process of data integration (data analytics) in solving the specific case study; does this tool involves the process of ETL or is it virtualized?

QUESTION 2

Would a logical data warehouse meet the need of your business case problem/ requirements? Or are you satisfied with the current tools?

QUESTION 3

How do you access the data from different sources? Or how do you extract data from different data sources? For example: Do you have an application where each of your data clients upload

data there, or do they send the data through emails or do you access their database to extract the required data you need?

QUESTION 4

After you are done with the analytics and presented the result, how do you deal the client data (method of disposing it after use)? What are the forms of agreement of disposing it or are they kept for future purposes?

QUESTION 5

Do you have any challenges related to data redundancy? What I mean is, based on the tools your organisation adopt, does it copy data (extraction) you need including data that might not be used at the end of the analysis? Do you have storage space issue? Is it in any way related to data redundancy?

If you answer is YES, please what measures have you considered in resolving this issue?

QUESTION 6

What other challenges do you face with the tools you are currently adopting?

QUESTION 7

How do you test for data validation? For example, are there issues related with data ambiguity from your different data sources? Do your different data sources have data formats with the same meaning of data (if source A uses the 12hrs time formats in their database and source B uses the 24hrs time formats) if your answer is NO how do you resolve such complexity)?

QUESTION 8

What changes would you like to make to your process of data integration if any? What are your recommendations?

The responses from the participants were analysed base on the following;

- a) *Is the traditional data warehouse involved (the use of ETL)?*
- b) *What challenges are they facing with this tool?*
- c) *Will logical data warehouse be a solution?*
- d) *Is data redundancy found as a challenge?*

TABLE 8: Outlines the responses received so far can be analysed

PARTICIPANTS	QUESTIONS ON ANALYSIS	RESPONSE
Business Intelligence department in UWS Paisley campus	a) Is the traditional data warehouse involved (the use of ETL)?	No data integration tool is required.
		Qlikview

	b) What tool is used for data analytics	Continuous
	c) What challenges are they facing with this tool?	awareness of development (version upgrades). Learning about the new version
	d) Will logical data warehouse be a solution?	No
	e) Is data redundancy involved? And is it found as a challenge?	Yes No Yes
	f) Is direct access to other data sources involved based on agreement?	
Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA)	a) Is the traditional data warehouse involved (the use of ETL)?	Yes
	b) What tool is used for data analytics	Oracle ETL
	c) What challenges are they facing with this tool?	Understanding not only the data sizes but frequency of data access. Also, heavy duty processing poses a challenge
	d) Will logical data	Yes

	warehouse be a solution?	Yes
	e) Is data redundancy involved? And is it found as a challenge	Yes Yes
	f) Is direct access to other data sources involved based on agreement?	
Chevron	a) Is the traditional data warehouse involved (the use of ETL)?	Yes
	b) What tool is used for data analytics?	Energy component, SAP, Oracle and SQL
	c) What challenges are they facing with this tool?.....	Data stored in different locations and not easily accessed
	d) Will logical data warehouse be a solution?	If it can solve the Problem, YES. No this is because there is a functional retention system.
	e) Is data redundancy involved?	Yes
	f) Is direct access to other data sources involved based on agreement?	
Department for Transport (Road Congestion Statistics)	a) Is the traditional data warehouse	Data warehousing is not involved. But data extraction is involved

	involved (the use of ETL)?	
	b) What tool is used for data analytics?	SQL Moving data into Google Cloud
	c) What challenges are they facing with this tool?	Platform which is more expensive if the data processing requires frequent interaction with the platform. No
	d) Will logical data warehouse be a solution?	Yes
	e) Is data redundancy involved? And is it found as a challenge?	Yes Yes, by Importing data to their SQL server.
	f) Is direct access to other data sources involved based on agreement?	Data is received via remote server monthly.
Azzurro Associates	a) Is the traditional data warehouse involved (the use of ETL)?	Yes
	b) What tool is used for data analytics?	Data bricks (python), and SQL
	c) What challenges are they facing with this tool?	Files coming in with different formats and different columns heading

		and it is time consuming to write a program each time new data are added in other to map those files.
	d) Will logical data warehouse be a solution?	No
	e) Is data redundancy involved? And is it found as a challenge?	Yes No

4.2.3 How the Participant's Interview Responses Answer Part of My Research Questions?

These research interview questions were designed in such a way to answer some of the research questions. Some of the interview questions aimed to find out if the organisation's data integration tools based on ETL process are the only techniques that can meet the business requirements in which organisation seems to be satisfied with. Also, the research questionnaire /interview questions were targeted to find out if organisations' satisfaction with the traditional data warehouse method are due to fear of change.

4.2.3.1 Research Questions

What are the problems associated when tools such as ETL precede big data analytics?

From the 5 participants below are the challenges outlined;

- Continuous awareness of development (version upgrades). Learning about the new version
- Understanding not only the data sizes but frequency of data access. Also, heavy duty processing poses a challenge.
- Data stored in different data locations within organisations, and they are not easily accessed.
- Moving data into Google Cloud Platform which is more expensive if the data processing requires frequent interaction with the platform.
- Data coming in with different formats and different columns heading and it is time consuming to write a program each time new data are added in other to map those files.

Observing from different responses, each firm has different challenges which some are partly related to each other. The challenges of understanding data size and speed of data access can be classified as big data challenges and one main challenge in big data integration is understanding the data. When data developers understand the business requirements and the

nature of data the organisation work with, they (data developer/ experts) will be able to design a system to be more efficient as well as effective for the business. Experts may be expensive for some organisation to hire.

Data stored in different locations: There are organisation as this that have various branches in different locations but operates together. However, data should easily be accessible despite the locations. Using this organisation challenge, their location varied from USA to Africa and other parts of the world, their rules for data management may also vary in different location but that can be challenging for one data manager/ data managers to access theses data on different databases and different location if effective SLAs are not in place. Cases such as these may require both logical data warehouse and traditional data warehouse (If trends, predictions are required) depending on the business requirements. For data to be easily accessed from disparate data sources the organisation may need to adopt data virtualisation methods thereby creating views based on queries demands and SLAs.

Other challenge is cost of using a platform when business requirements demand frequent interactions with google cloud platforms especially when live data is part of the business requirements.

Another challenge faced within organisation, is data from disparate sources when being extracted are in different formats and different column headings, it demands one having to re-write programming when new data are added. Also, the complexity and time taken in transforming and mapping data to suit business requirement and purpose aimed to achieve.

Does a centralised virtual database be the best solution to Big Data Integration?

Data virtualisation is not always the right solution for some organisations. From five (5) of the responses, three (3) out of five (5) responded “no”; as they think it won’t suit their day-to-day business requirements. Looking through the challenges outlined above some of these obstacles (like data coming through with different formats; Easy access to data from different locations) can be overcome by adopting data virtualisation techniques.

4.3 PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROPOSAL: A CASE STUDY

With the DAMS case study, the researcher aimed to use the case study to demonstrate the use of the proposed method of data Integration. Based on the case study requirements, imaginary data was used as real data collection was not possible. Using imaginary data, the researcher analysed the case study, provided a sample design, and analysed the outcome.

4.3.1 The software used in this prototype approach.

As stated in 3.2.3 Virtual data integration can still be achieved without the application of RESTView technology if the data consumer (client) accesses the data contributors’ database via HTTP interface.

For the proposed data integration demo, the thesis used following program below.

- C# programming code
- Microsoft SQL Server

ASP.net used the C# programming language to create web services/ web API and, also created the web applications that consumes the web API. Web API interacts with the Data sources to retrieve. This aspect was assumed to be the part performed by the data consumer. The URL originally should be provided by the data provider in which the data consumer adds to his web application in order to get data from the data contributor's view provided. The URL contain the login credentials to the specific view in a database agreed via SLA.

The web application created is assumed to be created by the data consumer who writes different queries and sent to the different databases to perform analysis which appears on his web application with the format the developer has designed for it to appear.

Microsoft SQL server used SQL programming language to create 3 different databases. Originally the three databases should be on different server or location but for the sake of demonstration of the proposed method of data integration the databases are in the same server. These databases are assumed to be the data contributors' databases.

4.4 DAMS BUSINESS CASE STUDY

A Digital Asset Management System is an essential component in the development of a contemporary, innovative 21st century learning and research environment. It is vital for sharing and preserving key digital resources created by UWS staff and students, and digital resources about the history of UWS, in a manner that complies with copyright, IPR and licensing requirements.

UWS theses, open educations resources (OERs), Special Collections items and archive footage of predecessor institution activity have the potential to be discovered by researchers, learners and alumni across the world, but they are currently hidden and/or distributed across many platforms. As such, there is no consistent approach for branding these items as having originated at UWS.

A Digital Asset Management System would allow us to:

- Centralise the storage of digital content created by UWS students and staff and digital content about the history of UWS;
- Share UWS digital content from one source to a global audience;
- Create a searchable portal to enable enhanced discovery of UWS digital content;
- Manage branding, promotion, copyright, IPR and licensing issues consistently and centrally;
- Create private storage spaces for digital objects intended only for UWS students and staff (e.g. exam past papers);
- Record accurate, clear and consistent metadata for UWS digital objects;
- Preserve UWS digital content for use, re-use or consultation by future learners, researchers and alumni.

4.4.1 DAMS Business Case Requirements

- Low data storage needed to be tackled
- Centralised storage of data
- Ability for data to be sharable

- Easy accessibility
- Searchable portal
- Integrated mechanism for recording metadata
- Digital storage of some data
- In – house online storage facility
- Suitable digital repository
- Data to be sharable (student or staff can upload content and share and should have a license.)

After discussion with the author of the case study it is observed that For UWS special collection, it is known that the data is not digitized and therefore, a database is needed.

• Theses and dissertation are everywhere or are in different department of the UWS and the collection is implemented as a shared folder. There is no link available to access dissertation archives by past students and alumni who have graduated or left the school for another. For the students to gain access to dissertation archives, they will have to make contact with the UWS staff in charge of library archives to get a copy of their dissertation.

• In the aspect of open education resource (OERs). UWS OERs does not have comment share license. It cannot be accessible by a non UWS student/staff; this means that if non GCU can access Glasgow OERs which is called edShare@GCU. The documents can be accessed by anyone, the documents can be edited, shared to other persons and references made to the document. Also, UWS OERs can be written by several academic staff and it is not on one platform.

• Examination papers are stored on Mahara, Mahara is an electronic platform but the problem with Mahara is that exam papers are only stored for about three years before being discarded.

Summary

DAMS have a lot of data especially some digital content that might be useful, but people do not know about because it lacks storage, so the system wants a platform to be user friendly and have meta-data about content. For digitized content, it is stored in files or shared files on people's PC's. Special collections are not digitized, so they require to be digitized and stored in one place. Examination papers are stored at people's PC so it is not easily accessible. Thesis and dissertation are stored in file folder, shared file meaning it is a PC.

Expectation

DAMS will need a platform that will allow public information accessible, and the information kept private via authorization. All the contents listed at the DAMS can be found in one department (library department)

4.4.2 Analysis of the Case Study

DAMS is a component for learning and research environment which should be useful for sharing and storing important resources provided by the staff and student of UWS.

Data Management Aspect Concerns

- UWS thesis and dissertation (EThOS)
- Open education resources (UWS OERs)
- Special collection website (SCW)
- Past-Exams papers (PEPs)
- Archived historical content (HC)

Problem / challenges faced

- No centralised storage of digital content
- Problem with the ability to share
- Restricted access in some case which is not supposed to be so
- No in-house online storage facility
- No integrated mechanism for recording metadata of a file
- No suitable digital repository

Research requirements

- My research aims to integrate data from heterogeneous sources whether it be the same platform or different platform without physically copying or moving data from its original source to a central data repository
- Aims to create easy accessibility
- Achieving logical data integration

DAMS requirements

- Low data storage needed to be tackled
- Centralised storage of data
- Ability for data to be sharable
- Easy accessibility
- Searchable portal
- Integrated mechanism for recording metadata
- Digital storage of some data
- In – house online storage facility
- Suitable digital repository
- Data to be sharable (student or staff can upload content and share and should have a license.)
- Thereby, reducing redundant data.

Some of the DAMS business case study requirement and similar with the research requirement. Figure 9 below is the suggestion provided as a solution to the challenges listed above. The figure 9 below shows that instead of centralising this information into one database or centralised data warehouse, data can be left with its original source and location and access will be made to each database via a mediator which is web -service. Analytics will then be performed logically, and the result will be presented. In **Figure 9** and **Figure 10** the database is assumed to be different server in this thesis for a demonstration of how integration is done

virtually, the combined data from different sources are then analysed and presented on a web application. The Figure 9 and Figure 10 shows the API is the web services acting as the mediator and point of communication between data contributors' database and data consumer's web application.

Figure 9 – Virtual Data Integration

With the case study in 4.2.2; a centralised virtual database can be applied and each database from the different sources will be completely self-sustained and functional. Operations will go on as normal on different databases without any interruption when live migration occurs.

Data virtualization will be designed as a direct link to multiple disparate sources system and this platform will provide virtual environment for accessing integrated information.

Figure 10: the proposed model of integration

Three databases were created with data of student stored in it. These databases are assumed to the three different data sources or servers that have no idea of what data each database contains. After the databases was created, web APIs as Web-services was created as a mediator / communicator channels to databases.

1. API sends queries to the three Databases to retrieve the Student, Exams and Department data in XML Format. The Data in the Databases can be consumed by web applications by calling the methods in API via the provided URLs.
2. The Web application (**Figure 13**) consumes the *three API urls* (Url 1, Url 2, Url 3) to retrieve the Student, Department and Exams data into three List Objects.
3. The Web application converts the three pieces of data (three List Objects) to three Tables.
4. The web application then passes the three Tables and the SQL Script written on the Web Page to a Stored Procedure.
5. Stored Procedures processes the Tables and Scripts as follows:
 - 5.1. Stored Procedure converts the three tables to temporary tables,
 - 5.2. Replaces the table names in the SQL Script with the Temporary table names created,
 - 5.3. Executes the script and returns a Table which is then presented below the SQL Script as shown below in **Figure 11**.

The figures below are explaining each step from step 1 to step 5.

```

public static List<Department> GetStudentByDepartment(int cn)
{
    List<Department> list = new List<Department>();
    if (cn == 1)
    {
        using (SqlConnection con = new SqlConnection(@"Data Source=DESKTOP-A06E6JI;Initial Catalog=Engineering;Integrated Security=True"))
        {
            con.Open();
            SqlCommand sql = new SqlCommand("SELECT * FROM dbo.vw_DepartmentStudents", con);

            SqlDataReader read = sql.ExecuteReader();
            while (read.Read())
            {
                Department stu = new Department();
                stu.StudentID = Convert.ToInt32(read[0]);
                stu.Faculty = read[1].ToString();
                stu.DepartmentID = Convert.ToInt32(read[2]);
                stu.DepartmentName = read[3].ToString();
                stu.DepartmentDescription = read[4].ToString();
                list.Add(stu);
            }
        }
    }
    return list;
}

```

Figure 11: API sends queries to the Databases and retrieves data in XML format. The API calling a view (highlighted in yellow) in the Engineering database (marked with blue ink)

Figure 12: A sample of Department data retrieved by the API call: that is, when the Web API interacts with Department’s database

The same process above applies as the web API calls the view provided from the **Exams Database and Student Database**, retrieving data and return data in XML formats on the web page.

The next step is that data consumer writes aggregated SQL Queries that combines data from three different databases and presents a result. This is done by the Web application shown in **Figure 13** consumes the three API urls (Url 1, Url 2, Url 3) to retrieve the Student, Department and Exams data into three List Objects. The SQL Queries were intended to get information about student by requesting for the Faculty, Department, Student ID, Student Name, Gender, Exams done, Exams Type and the Results of each Student. The inner join was combining Exams Database + Student Database + Department database. The presentation is presented on the format the data consumer designed has designed his web application to be.

Table Structures:
SELECT StudentID, Faculty, DepartmentID, DepartmentName, DepartmentDescription FROM dbo.Department
SELECT StudentID, FirstName, LastName, DateOfBirth, Gender FROM dbo.Student
SELECT StudentID, Exam, ExamDescription, Result, ExamDate FROM dbo.Exams

```

select
  c.Faculty
 ,c.DepartmentName as Department
 ,a.StudentID
 ,FirstName + ' ' + LastName as StudentName
 ,Gender
 ,Exam
 ,ExamDescription
 ,Result
from dbo.Exams as a
inner join dbo.Student as b on a.studentid = b.studentid
inner join dbo.Department as c on a.studentid = c.studentid
where Gender = 'male'
  
```

Execute Script

Faculty	Department	StudentID	StudentName	Gender	Exam	ExamDescription	Result
Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	PeterBeeston	Male	MECH 101	Fluid Mechanics	A
Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	PeterBeeston	Male	ENG 101	Use of english	B
Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	PeterBeeston	Male	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C
Engineering	Electrical	2019002	BillyLego	Male	ELECTRICAL 101	Electric Theorem	C
Engineering	Electrical	2019002	BillyLego	Male	ENG 101	Use of english	B
Engineering	Electrical	2019002	BillyLego	Male	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C
Engineering	Civil	2019004	JohnBlu	Male	CVE 101	Construction Theorem	D
Engineering	Civil	2019004	JohnBlu	Male	ENG 101	Use of english	A
Engineering	Civil	2019004	JohnBlu	Male	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C

Figure 13: when the 3 ULRs are used to call the three (3) different databases using the web application

The Figure above shows an SQL query filtered to produce result of male gender only. These results are originally meant to be from different server but in this case three different databases where queried and analytics was done virtually.

In the figure 14, the results included all students detail, both male and female. Note in the UWS database there are other data regarding students which are stored there but, in this case, we have assumed that part of the agreement is to provide views of specific information about students. Out of the data provided, the data consumer is querying to get information including Student faculty, department, ID, student name, gender, exam, exam description and their results from different data sources.

Table Structures:
SELECT StudentID, Faculty, DepartmentID, DepartmentName, DepartmentDescription FROM dbo.Department
SELECT StudentID, FirstName, LastName, DateOfBirth, Gender FROM dbo.Student
SELECT StudentID, Exam, ExamDescription, Result, ExamDate FROM dbo.Exams

```
select
  c.Faculty
  ,c.DepartmentName as Department
  ,a.StudentID
  ,FirstName + '' + LastName as StudentName
  ,Gender
  ,Exam
  ,ExamDescription
  ,Result
from dbo.Exams as a
inner join dbo.Student as b on a.studentid = b.studentid
inner join dbo.Department as c on a.studentid = c.studentid
```

Execute Script

Faculty	Department	StudentID	StudentName	Gender	Exam	ExamDescription	Result
Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	PeterBeeston	Male	MECH 101	Fluid Mechanics	A
Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	PeterBeeston	Male	ENG 101	Use of english	B
Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	PeterBeeston	Male	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C
Engineering	Electrical	2019002	BillyLego	Male	ELECTRICAL 101	Electric Theorem	C
Engineering	Electrical	2019002	BillyLego	Male	ENG 101	Use of english	B
Engineering	Electrical	2019002	BillyLego	Male	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C
Engineering	Electronics	2019003	MeganSteele	Female	ELECTRONICS 101	Electronic Theorem	C
Engineering	Electronics	2019003	MeganSteele	Female	ENG 101	Use of english	C
Engineering	Electronics	2019003	MeganSteele	Female	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C
Engineering	Civil	2019004	JohnBlu	Male	CVE 101	Construction Theorem	D
Engineering	Civil	2019004	JohnBlu	Male	ENG 101	Use of english	A
Engineering	Civil	2019004	JohnBlu	Male	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	C

Figure 14: Calls the three databases to return results including female students.

The URL is to be provided by the different data sources containing the access credentials to the views of the main databased. With the process in figure 15 same applies using the exams database URL and the student database URL.

```
public static List<Classes.DepartmentStudents> GetDepartmentStudents()
{
    List<Classes.DepartmentStudents> listDepartmentStudents = new List<DepartmentStudents>();
    string res;
    string api;
    HttpClient client = new HttpClient();
    client.BaseAddress = new Uri("http://localhost:59397/");
    api = "api/department";
    //api = "api/department?cn=1";
    HttpResponseMessage response = client.GetAsync(api).Result;
    //DataTable dt = new DataTable();
    if (response.IsSuccessStatusCode)
    {
        using (HttpContent content = response.Content)
        {
            Task<string> result = content.ReadAsStringAsync();
            res = result.Result;

            var processDataList = JsonConvert.DeserializeObject<List<Classes.DepartmentStudents>>(res);
            foreach (var processData in processDataList)
            {
                Classes.DepartmentStudents deptStudent = new DepartmentStudents();
                deptStudent.StudentID = processData.StudentID;
                deptStudent.Faculty = processData.Faculty;
                deptStudent.DepartmentID = processData.DepartmentID;
                deptStudent.DepartmentName = processData.DepartmentName;
                deptStudent.DepartmentDescription = processData.DepartmentDescription;
                listDepartmentStudents.Add(deptStudent);
            }
        }
    }
    return listDepartmentStudents;
}
```

Figure 15: WEB Client or Web Application consumes the API for Department data via URL (<http://localhost:59397/api/Department>).

The data retrieved from student database as well as exam and department databases are converted to tables.

```

public static DataTable CreateStudentTable(List<Classes.Student> listStudents)
{
    DataTable Students = new DataTable();
    DataColumn StudentID = new DataColumn("StudentID");
    DataColumn FirstName = new DataColumn("FirstName");
    DataColumn LastName = new DataColumn("LastName");
    DataColumn DateOfBirth = new DataColumn("DateOfBirth");
    DataColumn Gender = new DataColumn("Gender");

    StudentID.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.Int32");
    FirstName.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
    LastName.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
    DateOfBirth.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
    Gender.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");

    Students.Columns.Add(StudentID);
    Students.Columns.Add(FirstName);
    Students.Columns.Add(LastName);
    Students.Columns.Add(DateOfBirth);
    Students.Columns.Add(Gender);

    foreach (var student in listStudents)
    {
        DataRow row = Students.NewRow();
        row["StudentID"] = student.StudentID;
        row["FirstName"] = student.FirstName;
        row["LastName"] = student.LastName;
        row["DateOfBirth"] = student.DateOfBirth;
        row["Gender"] = student.Gender;

        Students.Rows.Add(row);
    }

    return Students;
}

```

Figure 16: Student Data converted to table.

The web client passes the three converted table highlighted in yellow and the SQL Script written on the web page to a Stored Procedure. There is a database has stored procedures that which performs the analytics. The analytics is performed virtually and does not leave a trace on the database. The database that has the stored procedure is meant to be on the data consumer's database.

```

public static DataTable AnalyzeTreatmentData(DataTable tblStudents, DataTable tblDept, DataTable tblExams, string sqlText)
{
    DataTable dt = new DataTable();
    using (SqlConnection con = new SqlConnection(@"Data Source=DESKTOP-A06E6JI;Initial Catalog=AnalysisDatabase;Integrated Security=True"))
    {
        con.Open();
        SqlCommand sql = new SqlCommand("sp_ProcessScript", con);
        sql.CommandType = CommandType.StoredProcedure;
        SqlParameter parameter;
        parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@SqlText", sqlText);
        parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Student", tblStudents);
        parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Department", tblDept);
        parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Exams", tblExams);
        SqlDataAdapter da = new SqlDataAdapter(sql);
        da.Fill(dt);
    }
    return dt;
}

```

Figure 17: The three Tables passed to a Stored Procedure.

Figure 18: Stored Procedure “sp_ProcessScript” to process the SQL Script and the Table variables passed by the Web Application

Observing **Figure 19** the database created is Engineering database, but data agreed via SLA from the Engineering database is Department; Hence, a view was created to access the views only and not a direct access to the engineering database

Figure 19: The View: SELECT * FROM Engineering.dbo.vw_DepartmentStudents called by the API to retrieve all students with their Departments data.

4.4.3 The ETL Alternative

The data integration requirement in the DAMS case study in 4.2.2 can also be achieved using traditional data warehouse approach, this means the data manager needs to create his own data warehouse, access the various data contributors' databases, extracts all information needed for analytics into a single physical location then queries from his own data warehouse.

Student Database Schema: Student details are in this database.

tblStudent	
StudentID	
FirstName	
LastName	
DoB	
Gender	
CreatedDate	

Figure 20: Table in student database containing student details

```
USE master
GO
CREATE DATABASE Student
GO

USE Student
GO

CREATE TABLE dbo.tblStudent
(
  StudentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblStudent_StudentID PRIMARY KEY,
  FirstName NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL,
  LastName NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL,
  DoB DATE NOT NULL,
  Gender NVARCHAR(10) NOT NULL,
  CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblStudent_CreatedDate DEFAULT GETDATE()
)
GO
```

The **Figure 21** showing the student database assumed that this database is in a different location owned by different organisation, so is seen to be one data source that the data consumer extracts the information needed for analytics from this student database.

	StudentID	FirstName	LastName	DoB	Gender	CreatedDate
1	2019001	Peter	Beeston	1978-01-21	Male	2020-11-04 18:14:52.297
2	2019002	Billy	Lego	1978-03-25	Male	2020-11-04 18:14:52.297
3	2019003	Megan	Steele	1978-06-19	Female	2020-11-04 18:14:52.297
4	2019004	John	Blu	1989-05-11	Male	2020-11-04 18:14:52.297

Figure 21: The student database showing the details of student in the database table

In **Figure 22** is another data source assumed to be from different organisation. It is the Engineering Database Schema; the data consumer extracts the information needed for analytics which are the Student's Faculty and department details that are located in this Engineering database.

Figure 22: the figure shows the information the data consumer needs from Engineering Database

```

USE master
GO
CREATE DATABASE Engineering
GO

USE Engineering
GO
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblDepartment
(
    DepartmentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblDepartment_DepartmentID PRIMARY KEY,
    Department NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL CONSTRAINT UN_tblDepartment_Department UNIQUE,
    DepartmentDescription NVARCHAR(200) NULL,
  
```

```

Faculty NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartment_Faculty DEFAULT
('Engineering'),
CreateDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartment_CreatedDate DEFAULT
GETDATE()
)
GO

CREATE TABLE dbo.tblDepartmentStudent
(
DepartmentStudentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT
PK_tblDepartmentStudent_DepartmentStudentID PRIMARY KEY,
DepartmentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT
FK_tblDepartmentStudent_tblDepartment_DepartmentID FOREIGN KEY REFERENCES
dbo.tblDepartment(DepartmentID),
StudentID INT NOT NULL,
CreateDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartmentStudent_CreatedDate DEFAULT
GETDATE()
)
GO

```

The SQL codes above shows the creation of the database table in **Figure 23**. The tables are holding the information needed for analysis.

Figure 23: The Engineering database showing the details of student in the database table.

In the Exams Database Schema: Student Exams details are in this database. The database comprises of 2 tables which are found in **Figure 24**.

Figure 24: The two tables in the exam database

```

USE master
GO

CREATE DATABASE Exams
GO

USE Exams
GO
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblExams
(
ExamID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblExams_ExamID PRIMARY KEY,
Exam NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL CONSTRAINT UN_tblExams_Exam UNIQUE,
ExamDescription NVARCHAR(200) NULL,
CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblExams_CreatedDate DEFAULT GETDATE()
)
GO
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblExamStudent
(
ExamStudentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblDepartmentStudent_ExamStudentID PRIMARY
KEY,
ExamID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT FK_tblExamStudent_tblExams_ExamID FOREIGN KEY
REFERENCES dbo.tblExams(ExamID),
StudentID INT NOT NULL,
Result NVARCHAR(10) NULL,
CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartmentStudent_CreatedDate DEFAULT
GETDATE()
)
GO
  
```

The SQL codes above shows the creation of the database tables in **Figure 25** and **Figure 26**. The tables are holding the information needed for analysis.

	ExamID	Exam	ExamDescription	CreatedDate
1	10001	MECH 101	Fluid Mechanics	2020-11-04 18:14:53.773
2	10002	ELECTRICAL 101	Electric Theorem	2020-11-04 18:14:53.773
3	10003	ELECTRONICS 101	Electronic Theorem	2020-11-04 18:14:53.773
4	10004	CVE 101	Construction Theorem	2020-11-04 18:14:53.773
5	10005	ENG 101	Use of english	2020-11-04 18:14:53.773
6	10006	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	2020-11-04 18:14:53.773

Figure 25: Details of data contained in the table created in Exams database

	ExamStudentID	ExamID	StudentID	Result	CreatedDate
1	1	10001	2019001	A	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
2	2	10005	2019001	B	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
3	3	10006	2019001	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
4	4	10002	2019002	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
5	5	10005	2019002	B	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
6	6	10006	2019002	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
7	7	10003	2019003	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
8	8	10005	2019003	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
9	9	10006	2019003	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
10	10	10004	2019004	D	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
11	11	10005	2019004	A	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797
12	12	10006	2019004	C	2020-11-04 18:14:53.797

Figure 26: Details of data contained in the other table created in Exams database

The data warehouse was then created with the schema that holds the data in which the integration will be from the three different data sources database tables (tblStudent, tblDepartmentStudent, tblDepartment, tblExamStudent and tblExams).

ResultAnalysis	
⚡ ID	▲
Faculty	
Department	
StudentID	
FirstName	
LastName	
Gender	
DateOfBirth	
ExamID	
Exam	
ExamDescription	
ExamDate	
Result	▼

Figure 27: ResultAnalysis Datawarehouse Schema

There are different data integrator software products such as Oracle data integrator, SAP Data Service, Microsoft SQL Server Integrator service and many more. **Figure 28** below is the Microsoft SQL Server Integration Package used to integrate the data from three assumed different data sources into the Data Warehouse to perform data analytics.

Figure 28: The SSIS package used to integrate three different Data sources

USE master
GO

```

CREATE DATABASE ResultAnalysis
GO

USE ResultAnalysis
GO

CREATE TABLE dbo.ResultAnalysis
(
    ID INT NOT NULL IDENTITY(1,1) PRIMARY KEY
, Faculty NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL
, Department NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL
, StudentID INT NOT NULL
, FirstName NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL
, LastName NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL
, Gender NVARCHAR(10) NOT NULL
, DateOfBirth DATE NOT NULL
, ExamID INT NOT NULL
, Exam NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL
, ExamDescription NVARCHAR(200) NULL
, ExamDate DATE NOT NULL
, Result NVARCHAR(10) NULL
)

```

ID	Faculty	Department	StudentID	FirstName	LastName	Gender	DateOfBirth	ExamID	Exam	ExamDescription	ExamDate	Result
1	Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	Peter	Beeston	Male	1978-01-21	10001	MECH 101	Fluid Mechanics	2020-11-04	A
2	Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	Peter	Beeston	Male	1978-01-21	10005	ENG 101	Use of english	2020-11-04	B
3	Engineering	Mechanical	2019001	Peter	Beeston	Male	1978-01-21	10006	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	2020-11-04	C
4	Engineering	Electrical	2019002	Billy	Lego	Male	1978-03-25	10005	ENG 101	Use of english	2020-11-04	B
5	Engineering	Electrical	2019002	Billy	Lego	Male	1978-03-25	10006	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	2020-11-04	C
6	Engineering	Electrical	2019002	Billy	Lego	Male	1978-03-25	10002	ELECTRICAL 101	Electric Theorem	2020-11-04	C
7	Engineering	Electronics	2019003	Megan	Steele	Female	1978-06-19	10003	ELECTRONICS 101	Electronic Theorem	2020-11-04	C
8	Engineering	Electronics	2019003	Megan	Steele	Female	1978-06-19	10005	ENG 101	Use of english	2020-11-04	C
9	Engineering	Electronics	2019003	Megan	Steele	Female	1978-06-19	10006	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	2020-11-04	C
10	Engineering	Civil	2019004	John	Blu	Male	1989-05-11	10005	ENG 101	Use of english	2020-11-04	A
11	Engineering	Civil	2019004	John	Blu	Male	1989-05-11	10004	CVE 101	Construction Theorem	2020-11-04	D
12	Engineering	Civil	2019004	John	Blu	Male	1989-05-11	10006	MATHS 101	Statistical Maths	2020-11-04	C

Figure 29: is the result of the analysis after the integration performed in **Figure 28**.

4.5 DISCUSSION AND RESEARCH RESULTS

This section discusses the outcome of the experimental approach of both the logical data warehouse approach and the traditional data warehouse or ETL approach and compare both approaches with the pro(s) and con(s).

4.5.2 Discussion and Findings

The first approach which is the logical data warehouse, used virtual data integration where the three different sources assumed to be in different locations and owned by different organisations, are left in their original locations and integration occurs virtually. In this approach,

1. Data is not yours, the data is only consumed and not stored therefore, the data from different data sources is not the responsibility of the data consumer for maintenance.
2. Web API is developed once, this means new data can be added without one rewriting new programming to accommodate new data source.
3. Web App designed can be accessed from any device like Laptop, desktop, mobile phone, tablets etc.

The second approach which is the Traditional Data Warehouse,

1. Data from the different data sources are integrated into a physical database (Data Warehouse). Which means the data consumer, or the client have the responsibility of data maintenance and security.
2. The Integration of data requires software products like Microsoft SQL Server Integration Services etc.
3. Data in the Data Warehouse can be consumed using Reporting software products like SQL Server Reporting Services, Power BI, Tableau, Qlickview, Excel etc.
4. Data can't be accessed in a mobile phone or tablet except for PC

4.5.2.1 Comparison between both Approaches

	Logical	Traditional Datawarehouse
1	Data is only consumed and not stored. Data Security and Integrity are guaranteed.	Data is stored, managed, and consumed. Data Security and Integrity must be designed and implemented. Datawarehouse must be created and managed too.
2	Data is accessed on mobile phones, PCs, tablets etc.	Data is accessed on PCs
3	Data can be accessed on web.	Data is accessed with Reporting Software products like excel, PowerBI, Tableau, SSRS etc.
4	Web App is developed using visual studio c#, java etc.	Datawarehouse is developed using Oracle, Microsoft SSMS etc. ETL is developed is developed using Microsoft SSIS. Reports are created using Reporting tools like SSRS, PowerBI, Excel etc.

5	Application Developer develops all that is needed to access and consumed data.	Data warehouse developer is needed to develop Datawarehouse. ETL developer is needed to develop the ETL solution. Report Developer to develop the Reporting solution.
6	Average salary of an Application developer: 30,000 pa	Average salary of a Datawarehouse developer: £33,000 pa Average salary of an ETL developer: 30,000 pa Average salary of a Report developer: 28,000 pa
7	Cost of Visual studio software:	Cost of Microsoft BI Stack (SSMS, SSIS, SSRS) software:

4.5.2.2 Cost Comparison Between Traditional Data Warehouse and Data Virtualization

With the different data integration techniques, more time may be required to model this different integration process and structure it into a unified one. Implementing Data Virtualization transforms these different data structures to a unified model (which will all be defined in the virtual tables) with import of less workloads and cost [79]. Using traditional data warehouse techniques, where data from desperate sources are extracted to a physical database, one needs to hire a data manager to manage, maintain and secure these data. The cost of hiring a database administrator is £30,933 [152] or SQL database developer is averagely £34,983 yearly [153]. We will also need a Business Intelligence (BI) Developer who will support information services such as ad hoc reporting, managing data modelling, data visualization and interactive dashboards. The yearly average price of hiring a BI Developer is £50,000 [154]. Also, the cost involved in data cleaning can depend on what is required but on average for 10,000 records of data it is within the range of \$5,000 to \$15,000. The cost of software or ETL tools used for example. The standard Microsoft SSIS is within £369.972 to £8,434.260 monthly. Other software tools for ETL like Matillion (Matillion uses cloud data warehouses) cost \$12,000 to \$48,000 per year depending on the plan and usage [155].

Virtual data warehouse (Data Virtualization) involves fewer phases which involves Data Capturing [this can be found in **section 4.3; Figure 11**]; Data cleansing and data joining [which can be found in **section 4.3; Figure 13**], data transformation which are defined in virtual tables [the process can be found in **section 4.3; Figure 15** and **Figure 16**].

For data virtualization/ logical data warehouse development we need a contractor for a period to develop the front-end and back-end web application. As part of the SLA involve the data contributor will be responsible for developing the API and the data contributors will provide the client with the URL to access the views. From a job site the cost of hiring a developer (Full Stack Developer) by average is £46,638 per annum [156]. The average cost of data virtualisation tools is \$48,000 but the cost can be flexible [157].

Compared to a research found in section 2.5, IT operating cost avoidance could amount to \$1,287,000, IT operating cost savings was 50% of over three years and there was an increase in end user productivity of \$3,834,000 over three years

4.5.2.3 Time consuming and Complexity Comparison between Traditional Data warehouse and Data Virtualisation

Using virtual data integration, each database component is self-sustained and functional. Data virtualization is designed as a direct link to multiple disparate sources system, it is a platform that provides a virtual environment for accessing integrated information. It uses virtual data models, virtual tables and there are no permanent connections with data sources. By accessing data from live sources only when required, it provides real -time data, and programmers do not need to re-design the system when new data sources are added.

The Web API used for approach 1 is developed once, this means new data can be added without a need to creating new queries or writing new programming code that will accept each new data. This saves time and reduces complexity.

With regards to approach 1 (data virtualization approach), all data are readily accessible to end users based on SLA between Data contributors and the Data consumer therefore eliminating the time taken in accessing separate servers and different application to move this that to a physical data warehouse.

Figure 35: Comparison of system architecture between Traditional Datawarehouse and Data Virtualization.

4.6 SUMMARY

In this chapter, section 4.2.3 the interview questionnaire responses were compared, and it is observed that ETL is widely known and used in most organisation and some organisations have little or no knowledge of logical data warehouse hence, they cannot tell for sure if the logical data warehouse techniques can be a solution to their business needs. This chapter also experimented not only the research proposed framework but also the traditional data warehouse framework to compare both experiments with regards to cost, complexity and reusability.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This section discusses the benefits and limitation of the research work. It also outlined the concluding remarks and recommendation for further work in the future.

5.1 Benefit of This Research

It is not always easy to access corporate data and make value out of it and that is the greatest challenge to producing effective reporting. In some organizations, information is difficult to access, or its availability is limited due to unwillingness of some firm to consolidate their data into a single data repository. Using this framework, data can be left in their original source rather than copying this data into one central database, the framework will allow one to access data through a mediator (Restif acting as micro-services) which creates a line of communication thereby leaving data in their original sources. It also reduces complexity in data modelling, and this is because Pyrrho Database (one of big data virtualization tools) which has RESTView technology does not need to re-write programming code. It promotes data transparency since there will be an agreement between the client and the contributor in providing the views according to SLA and therefore, the client works with the views provided. This framework can also allow one to interrogate live data. This framework reduces data redundancy since it doesn't leave a copy of the information from different sources on one central data repository.

In terms of security issues, when dealing with integration of data from many sources, security mechanisms should be considered at various levels. It is a major requirement for data scientist to think or analyse on how a development of tools will co-operate with diverse data sets and their security demands [73]. Some of the traditional security mechanisms adopted when using relational database is access control which can be role based or credential-based access control and this can feature in authentication, authorisation, and auditing [74] but these are not enough in the era of big data.

In big data analytics (process of data integration and warehouse), some of the security issues and challenges can vary from the distinction of data source and pattern and understanding the nature of data acquisition from diverse sources. The security challenges include how database storage can be protected; worrying about the end-point input validation; the real-time security and compliance monitoring; and how to detect metadata dependencies for confidentiality and security purpose [75]. With the proposed method of big data integration, the security challenge related to the data storage database will be minimised since the data owners are in-charge of their own data and using the logical data warehouse concept, data retrieved from different data source will not be store anywhere. Another security advantage it has is that data from various sources is secured and the clients only have access to the views in which the data owners are willing to give access to base on service level agreement.

5.2 Limitation of this Research

On the qualitative approach a dozen responses were initially required to make adequate analysis, group the responses on certain criteria, watch trends and note observation. But that wasn't totally possible. With regards to the interview questions responses had, most organisations depend on historical data for different purposed such as observing trends, predicting and for decision makings. Therefore, adopting data virtualization / logical data warehouse is not applicable to all big data firms.

With the Quantitative approach used in this research, if for example a query is required to join and draw out analysis from the information about students from different UWS database location/ sources, this can be done logically and be successful. But if the query required is far different from what is stated on the SLA's agreed between parties due to change of requirement, one need to rewrite and review new SLA's requesting agreed data structure or formats.

Having a single version of truth demands close cooperation between the data sources and data consumer, it is not always the case that both parties may agree to some terms such as data formats laid in SLA's. Another aspect that needs to be in for further research is the cost of SLA negotiation.

5.3 Conclusion

It is observed that many processes of data extraction involve the traditional method and do not have a virtualization or logical process of data analytics and the migration of data from different data sources have a copy in destination databases. This can lead to data redundancy, ETL process moving bulks of large data sets which runs on high end parallel computational hardware systems, and some techniques do not have easy access to data for decision processes. In this era of big data, the challenges expanded to the volume, velocity, and variety of data. Therefore, the implementation of big data integration involved the big data challenges, and this is a high security risk if all data are being extracted from the sources in making analysis and decision. Thus, introducing logical data warehouse (Data Virtualization) to traditional data integration provides a logical view of data, creates a single abstract layer between the data contributors and the data consumers in order to access data originating from different data applications sources. These data connect virtually to form virtual views and can be accessed via data services or APIs and can only be used based on the specific reason and specified queries agreed with the contributor. The quality of information is a problem when considering data sharing among different organization. Using our proposed model encourages easy access to data due to data sharing, reduces redundant data (by avoiding copying the whole data for analysis), reduces data complexity because it adopts easy semantics and for security purpose which uses logical warehouse whereby after data are used for the specific purpose it does not store.

In this dissertation, we addressed the different data management process and its' challenge. We reviewed different paper which adopted different techniques and stated the problem with each technique. After reviewing different papers, some of the challenges that were highlighted was data complexity which is as a result of unprecedented large-scale samples which appears in diversified data types and patterns and are in various data quality. The high dimensionality of data combined with large sample size of data has created these problems such as heavy computational cost and complexity. This research has implemented the use of data virtualisation which reduces complexity by tackling data volume in a way of promoting data from various sources should be kept in their various sources, but data consumer only uses the data that is required and agreed. Also, the new approach will not extract and use data that are required but also not storing this data as these data are accessed in real-time form their data sources. Another part of the approach is the implementation of SLA which agrees the data format and data type that each data contributor will design their database to be in. This method can also reduce data complexity as well. The cost of maintaining and managing the security of third-party data is minimised as the data owners are still in full control of data.

5.3.1 Contribution and Research Questions Addressed

The research employed the use of interview questions to acquire common challenges faced by organisation, with the responses some of the challenges faced are complexity and time taken in data transformation and mapping, cost of maintenance when dealing with third party's data, data accessibility challenges when data is needed for effective analytics for decision makers and not limited to understanding data size and frequency of data access needed. With this the research question "What are the problems associated when tools such as ETL precede big data analytics?" was addressed using the qualitative approach.

Deploying a prototype of the proposed framework, the result shows how data volume can be reduced by access source data via web API thereby leaving data in their various sources and only consuming data that is required. The implementation of the SLA and the terms involved demonstrates how data formats can be agreed and if agreed the complexity involve such as semantic ambiguity in Big Data variety is reduced. As data consumer accesses data directly from data sources with views and access control implemented, data response or data acquired are real-time data. Hence, the research questions "How will logical data warehouse be a solution to the V's (Volume, Velocity, Variety, of Big Data? And How should the problem of conflicting data formats and semantics (units, categories) be addressed?" is addressed using the prototype and implementation of SLAs terms and conditions.

In this framework, more research is needed in the security aspect to discover the security issues it might face using it.

5.4 Recommendation

This research described in this work projects some potential research directions in more in-depth research on data security in logical data warehouse and semantics alignment. Also, effective criteria for SLA's that will suit the majority of business requirement is a potential research focus.

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LIST of ABBREVIATIONS

API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business-to-Business
CEBR	Centre for Economics and Business Research
CSV	Comma Separated Value
DAMS	Digital Asset Management System
DBMS	Database Management System
DW	Data Warehouse
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
EDW	Enterprise Data Warehouse
ER	Electronic Records
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
GAV	Global – AS- View
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IBM	International Business Machines
IOT	Internet of Things
IPUMS	Integrated Public Used Micro-Data Services
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LAV	Local – As- View
LDW	Logical Data Warehouse
LOD	Link Open Data
NHS	National Health Service
MDA	Model Driven Architecture
MFIR	Meta Fusion Information Repository
OLAP	On-Line Analytical Processing
PC	Personal Computer
PPE	Personal protective equipment

RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
UK	United Kingdom
UML	Unified Modelling Language
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USA	United State of America
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
XML	Extensible Markup Language

ACHIEVING LOGICAL DATA WAREHOUSE IN THE PROCESS OF BIG DATA INTEGRATION AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS IN AN ORGANISATIONAL SECTOR: USING REST-VIEW TECHNOLOGY AS A STRATEGY FOR REDUCING DATA REDUNDANCY

What is the purpose of the study?

This research focuses on the integration of data into one virtual database using logical data warehousing technology in organisation sectors or departments. Applying *big live data* integration, data analytics can be carried out without copying data and also be in near real-time format to promote data correctness and avoid data redundancy.

The aim of my research is to achieve a logical data warehouse in the process of big data integration and big data analytics in organisational sectors: using RESTView technology as a strategy for reducing data redundancy as a challenge. Also to provide an easy way to access data through a centralised virtual database to be used in an organisation sector or as part of a smart city department.

Why have I been approached?

You have been approached because the researcher believes that your organisation may have a data integration project which could be used as a case study for this research projects.

What will I have to do and how long will it take?

The interviews are in two stages. The first stage, the researcher wishes to interview you about the nature of your data integration project and how data technology might be able to help. The second stage of the interview will take place some months later whereby the researchers have come up with ranges of options or proposals and will hope to get feedbacks from your organisation about those options proposed. This will take no longer than an hour and it will take place at your desired location. You may choose to have a face –to –face interview with the researcher or decide to answer the question on paper.

What will happen to the information collected?

The information that will be provided will not be in any form of embarrassment but in any case, it will be kept confidential. The researcher will study, analyse the information provided and the researcher will come up with sets of alternatives. The findings will help to understand the situation under study and the result of the study will help me to know whether it answers my research questions and may lead to the design of a better framework to bridge any gap found in the analytics tools and this is to achieve a doctoral degree [Ph.D.]. The information provided by any medium will be handled with strict confidentiality.

Declaration to participant if you take part in the research study, you have the right to:

- Refuse to answer any question even during your participation and to withdraw from the study at any time.
- Ask further questions that occurs to you about the study.
- Be given access to a summary of findings from study when it is concluded.

Who is responsible for your information or who to contact for more information?

The researcher: Chisom Ernesther Offia,

Email: [REDACTED]

Director of Studies: Professor Malcolm Crowe

Email: [REDACTED]

School of Engineering and computing

University of the West of Scotland (UWS), High St, Paisley PA1 2BE

1.1 CONSENT FORM

Hello, my names are Chisom Ernesther Offia and I am a research student in the School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland, UK. The aim of this research is to achieve a logical data warehouse in the process of big data integration and big data analytics in organisational sectors: one of the options is using RESTView technology as a strategy for reducing data redundancy as a challenge in data integration. Basically, this research is based on the process of data integration where the suppliers of data provide an access to data on request, rather than all data being copied to a large central repository.

It is important that you get a comprehensive reasons for this interview questions which are, to know if there are any case study or business requirements relating to data integration (and data analytics), to gain an understanding of the tools and processes you adopt in data analytics (in the process of data integration), to find out the possible challenges faced by various organisations with the tools you adopt, to analyse your case study and come up with potentials solutions or range of alternatives of different products that you can use, you will evaluate my options or proposals that am able to come up with (which will be the second interview after analysing your business requirements or case study) and draw out conclusions whether or not a logical data warehouse can be a majority solutions to the challenges outlined.

In the course of the interview, you have the right to adhere to the following;

Choose not to answer certain questions as well as making decisions to end the interview with any reasons.

You will remain anonymous throughout this research and no information will link back to you. The information given through this interview will be secured and be used for research purpose only. Once the information given to the researcher is analysed, it will be destroyed. The information will be seen by the researcher and her supervisor and there will be no third party handling your information.

Are you happy to continue?

Signed.....
Date.....

Please tick what means of Participation is convenient for you?

Face – to – Face Interview ()

Via Email ()

Via Phone Call ()

1.2 INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Dear Sir/ Madam

My names are Chisom Ernesther Offia and I am a research student in the School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences. The research has a need for investigating on what tools and how the process of data integration is done during analysis using data analytical tools in your organisation. The research is based on the process of data integration where the suppliers of data provide access to data on request, rather than all data being copied to a large central repository. The researcher is looking for different case studies whereby organisation's business case requirements involve data integration. A hypothesis in the research is that, such cooperation would be facilitated by the use of logical data warehousing instead of maintaining copies of data. In some ways, the arms-length collection of the datasets by organisational bodies such as yours might model part of this process.

Introductory Questions

Name Of Organisation -----

Position -----

QUESTION 1

Are there business case data requirements in your organisation that may require data integration? If YES, what technology or tools do you adopt in the process of data integration (data analytics) in solving the particular case study; does this tool involves the process of ETL or is it virtualized?

QUESTION 2

Would a logical data warehouse meet the need of your business case problem/ requirements? Or are you satisfied with the current tools?

QUESTION 3

How do you access the data from different sources? Or how do you extract data from different data sources? For example: Do you have an application where each of your data clients upload data there, or do they send the data through emails or do you access their database to extract the required data you need?

QUESTION 4

After you are done with the analytics and presented the result, how do you deal the client data (method of disposing it after use)? What are the forms of agreement of disposing it or are they kept for future purposes?

QUESTION 5

Do you have any challenges related to data redundancy? What I mean is, based on the tools your organisation adopt, does it copy data (extraction) you need including data that might not be used at the end of the analysis? Do you have storage space issue? Is it in any way related to data redundancy?

If you answer is YES, please what measures have you considered in resolving this issue?

QUESTION 6

What other challenges do you face with the tools you are currently adopting?

QUESTION 7

How do you test for data validation? For example, are there issues related with data ambiguity from your different data sources? Do your different data sources have data formats with the same meaning of data (if source A uses the 12hrs time formats in their database and source B uses the 24hrs time formats) if your answer is NO how do you resolve such complexity)?

QUESTION 8

What changes would you like to make to your process of data integration if any? What are your recommendations?

APPENDIX 2

1.1 DATABASE CODES

```
USE master
GO
```

```
CREATE DATABASE Student
GO
```

```
USE Student
GO
```

```
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblStudent
(
  StudentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblStudent_StudentID PRIMARY KEY,
  FirstName NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL,
  LastName NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL,
  DoB DATE NOT NULL,
  Gender NVARCHAR(10) NOT NULL,
  CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblStudent_CreatedDate DEFAULT GETDATE()
)
GO
```

```
CREATE VIEW dbo.vw_Student
AS
SELECT StudentID,FirstName,LastName,DoB,Gender FROM dbo.tblStudent
GO
```

```
INSERT INTO dbo.tblStudent
SELECT 2019001, 'Peter', 'Beeston', '1978-01-21', 'Male', GETDATE() UNION
SELECT 2019002, 'Billy', 'Lego', '1978-03-25', 'Male', GETDATE() UNION
SELECT 2019003, 'Megan', 'Steele', '1978-06-19', 'Female', GETDATE() UNION
SELECT 2019004, 'John', 'Blu', '1989-05-11', 'Male', GETDATE()
GO
```

```
USE master
GO
```

```
CREATE DATABASE Engineering
GO
```

```
USE Engineering
GO
```

```
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblDepartment
(
  DepartmentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblDepartment_DepartmentID PRIMARY KEY,
  Department NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL CONSTRAINT UN_tblDepartment_Department UNIQUE,
  DepartmentDescription NVARCHAR(200) NULL,
  Faculty NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartment_Faculty DEFAULT
('Engineering'),
  CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartment_CreatedDate DEFAULT
GETDATE()
)
```

```
GO
```

```
INSERT INTO dbo.tblDepartment(DepartmentID,Department,DepartmentDescription)
SELECT 101,'Mechanical','Study of Mechanics' UNION
SELECT 102,'Electrical','Study of Electrical Principles' UNION
SELECT 103,'Electronics','Study of Electrical Principles' UNION
SELECT 104,'Civil','Study of Construction Principles'
GO
```

```
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblDepartmentStudent
(
    DepartmentStudentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT
    PK_tblDepartmentStudent_DepartmentStudentID PRIMARY KEY,
    DepartmentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT
    FK_tblDepartmentStudent_tblDepartment_DepartmentID FOREIGN KEY REFERENCES
    dbo.tblDepartment(DepartmentID),
    StudentID INT NOT NULL,
    CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartmentStudent_CreatedDate DEFAULT
    GETDATE()
)
GO
```

```
INSERT INTO dbo.tblDepartmentStudent
SELECT 1,101,2019001,GETDATE() UNION
SELECT 2,102,2019002,GETDATE() UNION
SELECT 3,103,2019003,GETDATE() UNION
SELECT 4,104,2019004,GETDATE()
GO
```

```
CREATE VIEW dbo.vw_DepartmentStudents
AS
SELECT
    A.StudentID
    ,B.Faculty
    ,B.DepartmentID
    ,B.Department
    ,B.DepartmentDescription
FROM dbo.tblDepartmentStudent AS A
INNER JOIN dbo.tblDepartment AS B ON A.DepartmentID = B.DepartmentID
GO
```

```
USE master
GO
```

```
CREATE DATABASE Exams
GO
```

```
USE Exams
GO
```

```
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblExams
(
    ExamID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblExams_ExamID PRIMARY KEY,
    Exam NVARCHAR(100) NOT NULL CONSTRAINT UN_tblExams_Exam UNIQUE,
    ExamDescription NVARCHAR(200) NULL,
    CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblExams_CreatedDate DEFAULT GETDATE()
)
```

```
)  
GO
```

```
INSERT INTO dbo.tblExams  
SELECT 10001, 'MECH 101', 'Fluid Mechanics', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 10002, 'ELECTRICAL 101', 'Electric Theorem', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 10003, 'ELECTRONICS 101', 'Electronic Theorem', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 10004, 'CVE 101', 'Construction Theorem', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 10005, 'ENG 101', 'Use of english', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 10006, 'MATHS 101', 'Statistical Maths', GETDATE()  
GO
```

```
CREATE TABLE dbo.tblExamStudent  
(  
ExamStudentID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT PK_tblDepartmentStudent_ExamStudentID PRIMARY  
KEY,  
ExamID INT NOT NULL CONSTRAINT FK_tblExamStudent_tblExams_ExamID FOREIGN KEY  
REFERENCES dbo.tblExams(ExamID),  
StudentID INT NOT NULL,  
Result NVARCHAR(10) NULL,  
CreatedDate DATETIME NOT NULL CONSTRAINT DF_tblDepartmentStudent_CreatedDate DEFAULT  
GETDATE()  
)  
GO
```

```
INSERT INTO dbo.tblExamStudent  
SELECT 1,10001,2019001, 'A', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 2,10005,2019001, 'B', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 3,10006,2019001, 'C', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 4,10002,2019002, 'C', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 5,10005,2019002, 'B', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 6,10006,2019002, 'C', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 7,10003,2019003, 'C', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 8,10005,2019003, 'C', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 9,10006,2019003, 'C', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 10,10004,2019004, 'D', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 11,10005,2019004, 'A', GETDATE() UNION  
SELECT 12,10006,2019004, 'C', GETDATE()  
GO
```

```
CREATE VIEW dbo.vw_ExamStudents  
AS  
SELECT  
    A.StudentID  
    ,B.Exam  
    ,B.ExamDescription  
    ,A.Result  
    ,CONVERT(VARCHAR(10),A.CreatedDate,25) AS ExamDate  
FROM dbo.tblExamStudent AS A  
INNER JOIN dbo.tblExams AS B ON A.ExamID = B.ExamID  
GO
```

```
use master  
GO
```

```
CREATE DATABASE AnalysisDatabase
GO
```

```
USE AnalysisDatabase
GO
```

```
CREATE TYPE [dbo].[Student] AS TABLE(
    StudentID int NOT NULL
    ,FirstName nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,LastName nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,DateOfBirth nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,Gender nvarchar(10) NOT NULL
)
GO
```

```
CREATE TYPE [dbo].[Department] AS TABLE(
    StudentID int NOT NULL
    ,Faculty nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,DepartmentID int NOT NULL
    ,DepartmentName nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,DepartmentDescription nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
)
GO
```

```
CREATE TYPE [dbo].[Exams] AS TABLE(
    StudentID int NOT NULL
    ,Exam nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,ExamDescription nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,Result nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
    ,ExamDate nvarchar(100) NOT NULL
)
GO
```

```
CREATE PROCEDURE [dbo].[sp_ProcessScript]
(
    @SqlText NVARCHAR(MAX)
    ,@Student dbo.Student READONLY

```

```

,@Department dbo.Department READONLY
,@Exams dbo.Exams READONLY
)
AS
BEGIN TRAN
SELECT @SqlText = RTRIM(LTRIM(@SqlText))
SELECT @SqlText = REPLACE(@SqlText, 'dbo.Student', '#Student')
SELECT @SqlText = REPLACE(@SqlText, 'dbo.Department', '#Department')
SELECT @SqlText = REPLACE(@SqlText, 'dbo.Exams', '#Exams')

IF(ISNULL(@SqlText, '') <> '')
BEGIN
    SELECT * INTO #Student FROM @Student
    SELECT * INTO #Department FROM @Department
    SELECT * INTO #Exams FROM @Exams
END
ELSE
    SELECT @SqlText = 'SELECT ''No Sql Script was passed for processing....'' AS
EmptyText'
EXECUTE sys.sp_executesql @SqlText

COMMIT TRAN
GO

USE master
GO

DROP DATABASE Student
GO

DROP DATABASE Engineering
GO

DROP DATABASE Exams
GO

DROP DATABASE AnalysisDatabase
GO

```

1.2 WEB APPLICATION CODES

Default.aspx.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Data;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.HtmlControls;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;

namespace WebClient_UWS
{
    public partial class Default : System.Web.UI.Page
    {
        protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
        }

        protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            try
            {
                List<Classes.Student> listStudents =
Classes.ProcessData.GetStudentDetails();
                List<Classes.DepartmentStudents> listStudentsDept =
Classes.ProcessData.GetDepartmentStudents();
                List<Classes.ExamsStudents> listStudentExams =
Classes.ProcessData.GetExamReults();

                DataSet ds =
Classes.DataLayer.AnalyzeTreatmentData(Classes.DataLayer.CreateStudentTable(listStuden
ts),
                Classes.DataLayer.CreateDepartmentsTable(listStudentsDept),
Classes.DataLayer.CreateExamsTable(listStudentExams), TextBox1.Text);

                for (int i = 0; i < ds.Tables.Count; i++)
                {
                    GridView gv = new GridView();
                    gv.DataSource = ds.Tables[i];
                    gv.DataBind();
                    form1.Controls.Add(gv);

                    HtmlGenericControl p = new HtmlGenericControl("p");
                    p.InnerText = " ";
                    form1.Controls.Add(p);
                }
            }
            catch(Exception ex)
            {
                Response.Write("Error: "+ex.Message);
            }
        }
    }
}
```

BusinessObjects.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;

namespace WebClient_UWS.Classes
{
    public class BusinessObjects
    {
    }

    public class Student
    {
        public int StudentID { get; set; }
        public string FirstName { get; set; }
        public string LastName { get; set; }
        public string DateOfBirth { get; set; }
        public string Gender { get; set; }
    }

    public class DepartmentStudents
    {
        public int StudentID { get; set; }
        public string Faculty { get; set; }
        public int DepartmentID { get; set; }
        public string DepartmentName { get; set; }
        public string DepartmentDescription { get; set; }
    }

    public class Department
    {
        public int DepartmentID { get; set; }
        public string DepartmentName { get; set; }
        public string DepartmentDescription { get; set; }
        public string Faculty { get; set; }
    }

    public class ExamsStudents
    {
        public int StudentID { get; set; }
        public string Exam { get; set; }
        public string ExamDescription { get; set; }
        public string Result { get; set; }
        public string ExamDate { get; set; }
    }
}
```

ProcessData.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;
using System.Net.Http;
using System.Data;
using System.Threading.Tasks;
using System.Web.Script.Serialization;
using Newtonsoft.Json;

namespace WebClient_UWS.Classes
{
    public class ProcessData
    {

        public static List<Classes.Student> GetStudentDetails()
        {
            List<Classes.Student> listStudents = new List<Student>();
            string res;
            string api;
            HttpClient client = new HttpClient();
            client.BaseAddress = new Uri("http://localhost:59397/");
            api = "api/student";

            HttpResponseMessage response = client.GetAsync(api).Result;
            //DataTable dt = new DataTable();
            if (response.IsSuccessStatusCode)
            {
                using (HttpContent content = response.Content)
                {
                    Task<string> result = content.ReadAsStringAsync();
                    res = result.Result;

                    var processDataList =
                    JsonConvert.DeserializeObject<List<Classes.Student>>(res);
                    foreach (var processData in processDataList)
                    {
                        Classes.Student student = new Student();
                        student.StudentID = processData.StudentID;
                        student.FirstName = processData.FirstName;
                        student.LastName = processData.LastName;
                        student.DateOfBirth = processData.DateOfBirth;
                        student.Gender = processData.Gender;
                        listStudents.Add(student);
                    }
                }
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

        return listStudents;
    }

    public static List<Classes.DepartmentStudents> GetDepartmentStudents()
    {
        List<Classes.DepartmentStudents> listDepartmentStudents = new
List<DepartmentStudents>();
        string res;
        string api;
        HttpClient client = new HttpClient();
        client.BaseAddress = new Uri("http://localhost:59397/");
        api = "api/department";
        //api = "api/department?cn=1";
        HttpResponseMessage response = client.GetAsync(api).Result;
        //DataTable dt = new DataTable();
        if (response.IsSuccessStatusCode)
        {
            using (HttpContent content = response.Content)
            {
                Task<string> result = content.ReadAsStringAsync();
                res = result.Result;

                var processDataList =
JsonConvert.DeserializeObject<List<Classes.DepartmentStudents>>(res);
                foreach (var processData in processDataList)
                {
                    Classes.DepartmentStudents deptStudent = new
DepartmentStudents();
                    deptStudent.StudentID = processData.StudentID;
                    deptStudent.Faculty = processData.Faculty;
                    deptStudent.DepartmentID = processData.DepartmentID;
                    deptStudent.DepartmentName = processData.DepartmentName;
                    deptStudent.DepartmentDescription =
processData.DepartmentDescription;
                    listDepartmentStudents.Add(deptStudent);
                }
            }
        }
        return listDepartmentStudents;
    }

    public static List<Classes.ExamsStudents> GetExamReults()
    {
        List<Classes.ExamsStudents> listExams = new List<ExamsStudents>();
        string res;
        string api;
        HttpClient client = new HttpClient();
        client.BaseAddress = new Uri("http://localhost:59397/");
        api = "api/exams";

        HttpResponseMessage response = client.GetAsync(api).Result;
        //DataTable dt = new DataTable();
        if (response.IsSuccessStatusCode)
        {
            using (HttpContent content = response.Content)
            {
                Task<string> result = content.ReadAsStringAsync();
                res = result.Result;

```



```

using System.IO;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Data;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace WebClient_UWS.Classes
{
    public class DataLayer
    {

        public static DataSet AnalyzeTreatmentData(DataTable tblStudents, DataTable
tblDept, DataTable tblExams, string sqlText)
        {
            DataSet dt = new DataSet();
            using (SqlConnection con = new SqlConnection(@"Data Source=DESKTOP-
A06E6JI;Initial Catalog=AnalysisDatabase;Integrated Security=True"))
            {
                con.Open();
                SqlCommand sql = new SqlCommand("sp_ProcessScript", con);
                sql.CommandType = CommandType.StoredProcedure;
                SqlParameter parameter;
                parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@SqlText", sqlText);
                parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Student", tblStudents);
                parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Department", tblDept);
                parameter = sql.Parameters.AddWithValue("@Exams", tblExams);
                SqlDataAdapter da = new SqlDataAdapter(sql);
                da.Fill(dt);
            }
            return dt;
        }

        public static DataTable
CreateDepartmentsTable(List<Classes.DepartmentStudents> listDepartments)
        {
            DataTable Dept = new DataTable();
            DataColumn StudentID = new DataColumn("StudentID");
            DataColumn Faculty = new DataColumn("Faculty");
            DataColumn DepartmentID = new DataColumn("DepartmentID");
            DataColumn DepartmentName = new DataColumn("DepartmentName");
            DataColumn DepartmentDescription = new
DataColumn("DepartmentDescription");

            StudentID.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.Int32");
            Faculty.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
            DepartmentID.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.Int32");
            DepartmentName.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
            DepartmentDescription.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");

            Dept.Columns.Add(StudentID);
            Dept.Columns.Add(Faculty);
            Dept.Columns.Add(DepartmentID);
            Dept.Columns.Add(DepartmentName);
            Dept.Columns.Add(DepartmentDescription);
        }
    }
}

```

```

foreach (var dpt in listDepartments)
{
    DataRow row = Dept.NewRow();
    row["StudentID"] = dpt.StudentID;
    row["Faculty"] = dpt.Faculty;
    row["DepartmentID"] = dpt.DepartmentID;
    row["DepartmentName"] = dpt.DepartmentName;
    row["DepartmentDescription"] = dpt.DepartmentDescription;

    Dept.Rows.Add(row);
}

return Dept;
}

public static DataTable CreateStudentTable(List<Classes.Student> listStudents)
{
    DataTable Students = new DataTable();
    DataColumn StudentID = new DataColumn("StudentID");
    DataColumn FirstName = new DataColumn("FirstName");
    DataColumn LastName = new DataColumn("LastName");
    DataColumn DateOfBirth = new DataColumn("DateOfBirth");
    DataColumn Gender = new DataColumn("Gender");

    StudentID.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.Int32");
    FirstName.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
    LastName.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
    DateOfBirth.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
    Gender.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");

    Students.Columns.Add(StudentID);
    Students.Columns.Add(FirstName);
    Students.Columns.Add(LastName);
    Students.Columns.Add(DateOfBirth);
    Students.Columns.Add(Gender);

    foreach (var student in listStudents)
    {
        DataRow row = Students.NewRow();
        row["StudentID"] = student.StudentID;
        row["FirstName"] = student.FirstName;
        row["LastName"] = student.LastName;
        row["DateOfBirth"] = student.DateOfBirth;
        row["Gender"] = student.Gender;

        Students.Rows.Add(row);
    }

    return Students;
}

public static DataTable CreateExamsTable(List<Classes.ExamsStudents>
listExams)
{
    DataTable Exams = new DataTable();
    DataColumn StudentID = new DataColumn("StudentID");
    DataColumn Exam = new DataColumn("Exam");

```

```

        DataColumn ExamDescription = new DataColumn("ExamDescription");
        DataColumn Result = new DataColumn("Result");
        DataColumn ExamDate = new DataColumn("ExamDate");

        StudentID.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.Int32");
        Exam.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
        ExamDescription.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
        Result.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");
        ExamDate.DataType = System.Type.GetType("System.String");

        Exams.Columns.Add(StudentID);
        Exams.Columns.Add(Exam);
        Exams.Columns.Add(ExamDescription);
        Exams.Columns.Add(Result);
        Exams.Columns.Add(ExamDate);

        foreach (var exm in listExams)
        {
            DataRow row = Exams.NewRow();
            row["StudentID"] = exm.StudentID;
            row["Exam"] = exm.Exam;
            row["ExamDescription"] = exm.ExamDescription;
            row["Result"] = exm.Result;
            row["ExamDate"] = exm.ExamDate;

            Exams.Rows.Add(row);
        }

        return Exams;
    }
}

```